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A Review of Natural Capital in the UK and Scottish Policy Context

A report for the RESAS Strategic Research Programme project 'Bringing in Participatory Approaches to Widen the Scope of Natural Capital Valuation' (JHI-D5-1)

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22nd November 2022

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Katy Joyce. 2022 A review of Natural Capital in the UK and Scottish policy context.
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Table of Contents

Introduction	4
Conceptual Background	4
CHAPTER 1: METHODS	5
• 1.1 Research Concept	5
• 1.2 Identification of Documents for Analysis.....	6
• 1.3 Structure of the Report.....	7
• 1.4 Descriptive Analysis of Reviewed Studies.....	8
CHAPTER 2: RESULTS	9
2.1 Natural Capital in Overarching Policy and Across Policy Sectors	9
• 2.11 Key Instruments in an Emerging Area of Focus on Natural Capital in the UK	9
• 2.12 Natural Capital Approaches in Five UK Policy Sectors	11
▪ <i>UK Economic Policy</i>	11
▪ <i>UK Climate Change Policy</i>	12
▪ <i>UK Planning and Land Use Policy</i>	12
▪ <i>UK Agriculture Policy</i>	12
▪ <i>UK Conservation and Biodiversity Policy</i>	13
• 2.13 Key Instruments in an Emerging Area of Focus on Natural Capital in Scotland	13
• 2.14 Natural Capital in Five Scottish Policy Sectors	14
▪ <i>Scottish Economic Policy</i>	14
▪ <i>Scottish Climate Change Policy</i>	15
▪ <i>Scottish Planning and Land Use Policy</i>	15
▪ <i>Scottish Agriculture Policy</i>	15
▪ <i>Scottish Conservation and Biodiversity Policy</i>	17
2.2 Natural Capital in Forest Policy	18
• 2.21 UK Forest Policy	18
• 2.22 Scottish Forest Policy	19
2.3 Public Technical and Finance Mechanisms for Supporting Landowners with Natural Capital Approaches	20
• 2.31 UK Support Mechanisms.....	21
• 2.32 Scottish Support Mechanisms.....	23
2.4 Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches	26
• 2.41 Private Sector Involvement in the UK.....	26
• 2.42 Private Sector Involvement in Scotland	26
CHAPTER 3: SYNTHESIS AND DISCUSSION	27

3.31 Natural Capital in High Level and Secondary Policy Across Selected UK Policy Sectors.....	27
3.32 Natural Capital in High Level and Secondary Policy Across Selected Scottish Policy Sectors ..	29
3.33 Natural Capital in Forest Policy	31
• UK Forest Policy	31
• Scottish Forest Policy	32
3.34 Public Mechanisms for Supporting Landowners with Natural Capital Approaches	33
• UK Technical and Financial Support Mechanisms	33
• Scottish Technical and Financial Support Mechanisms	34
3.35 Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches	35
• Private Sector Involvement in the UK.....	36
• Private Sector Involvement in Scotland.....	37
3.36 Limitations of the Review and Opportunities for Future Natural Capital Research in the Scottish and UK Policy Context	38
CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	39
Acknowledgement	41
Bibliography.....	41

Introduction

Based on key recommendations from the Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]) this report considers how cross-sectoral policy might usefully contribute to the prioritisation, protection and enhancement of nature and natural capital in Scotland. Using inductive reasoning and a snowball approach it features a search and analysis of policy documents and grey literature from the UK and from Scotland itself. It employs a typology of government decision making around the incorporation of natural capital approaches into policy from the Global Green Growth Institute (GGKI, 2020) as a framework for analysis of the extent and ways in which this has occurred across five key policy sectors and includes a particular additional focus on the forestry sector. It explores both public and private sector support mechanisms for, and involvement in, operationalising natural capital approaches on the ground, and considers the extent to which natural capital related activity in the UK influences or incentivises the Scottish policy context. Although it identifies an emerging group of dedicated natural capital policy instruments and activities and a willingness to explore alternative conceptions of economic success and inclusive wealth from both governments it reveals a current failure of high-level policy to produce a trickle-down into secondary policy due in-part to a lack of regulatory impetus, and as such, instances of on-the-ground operational activity remain uncommon. Positive signs that change may be coming, particularly in the agriculture and forestry sectors, are explored. The report finds that 'collective action' (Dasgupta, 2021 [1]) which facilitates joined-up thinking and action across sectors and stakeholders and the drawing of links between policy levels and activities to highlight pathways to implementation may be the key to operationalising what is, so far, a largely conceptual approach.

Conceptual Background

The Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]) provided a wake-up call which outlined humanity's unsustainable overconsumption of the Earth's natural capital, the imbalance between this and the natural resources the Earth can comfortably afford to provide, and the extent to which this 'impact inequality' (Dasgupta, 2021, p.117 [1]) is embedded in the economic thinking currently at the root of the way we construct our lives, do business, and for governments, design and enact policy. The review points to a pervasive and fundamental institutional failure to be accountable for prioritising the protection of a broader set of values in nature than just their monetary value upon exploitation as a primary cause of this inequality. This has led to a systematic decline in the quantity, condition and functionality of natural capital for providing crucially important ecosystem services and the benefits they bestow. The Review calls for a recognition of economics as 'embedded within nature' rather than external to it (Dasgupta, 2021, p.2 [2]) and that exhausting our natural capital impacts the Earth, our economies and the future of humanity. Our current norms of consumption and production must be reconstructed based on a deep shift in thinking about what constitutes wealth and economic success. The Review therefore situates natural capital as central to a new focus on 'inclusive wealth', which goes beyond measures of GDP to consider the economic and wider benefits of investing in nature and highlights the perilous economic (and broader) risks and trade-offs inherent in policy decision making that fails to include proper accounting and valuation of, and consideration of interactions with, natural assets (Dasgupta, 2021, p.4 [2]). Although we are at a relatively early stage in our understanding of how to account for and value natural capital, and how to use this knowledge to positively influence our decision making, useful tools, frameworks and case-studies exist and research to increase our capabilities in these areas is rapidly advancing. Collective, inclusive action which attempts to

incentivise, operationalise, regulate and trial these approaches from institutions across all sectors, public and private, is needed for the protection and enhancement of our natural capital for future generations; with this in mind, policy must be prepared to be firmly positioned as a driver of transformational change.

CHAPTER 1: METHODS

- 1.1 Research Concept

Scotland is keen to incorporate natural capital approaches at a policy level and indeed, to become a world leader in this respect. This report examines the policy context in which this endeavour is taking place. Since Scotland must comply with key overarching UK policies, the UK's commitment to natural capital approaches, the extent to which policy incorporates them and is or is not operationalised and the impact this may have had on Scottish policy, via regulation or otherwise, is examined. Within this context the extent to which Scotland has itself embedded natural capital approaches within overarching and secondary policy and operationalised these is explored.

Further, since relevant policies act to instrumentalise approaches, public mechanisms, which facilitate landowners to implement natural capital approaches on their land either through technical or financial support, are considered. Finally, through a process of inductive research it has become clear that both the UK and Scotland aim to operationalise natural capital approaches in part by seeking private sector investment, and indeed that private sector involvement may provide another area of financial support or obligatory impetus for landowners in this regard, and as such private sector involvement in natural capital approaches is also examined.

Since it is difficult at times to separate UK and English policy (Defra, for example, has made both UK and English policy contributions and some documents, for example the 25 Year Plan (HM Government, 2018 [1]), refer in part to the UK and in part to England), we have included discussion of some key English policies and support offerings as well where, for example, they are accessible to anyone in the UK and including in Scotland (ENCA, for example) or where they serve to illustrate the general will or approach of the UK government in embedding natural capital approaches in policy.

As such the report addresses the following five research questions:

- To what extent and in what ways are natural capital approaches conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in overarching policy?
- To what extent and in what ways are natural capital concepts conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in secondary policy?
- To what extent and in what ways are natural capital concepts conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in forest policy?
- What technical or financial support is available in the public sphere for landowners to operationalise natural capital approaches?
- What level of involvement does the private sector have in natural capital approaches and how is this facilitated?

In order to answer these questions, we have chosen to examine government policy documents and grey literature, rather than reviewing academic literature on the topic as we intended to conduct a

primary rather than secondary review. Since we are interested not only in how natural capital approaches are embedded in policy but also in whether, and how, they are operationalised with particular focus on the forest sector, we have also explored the extent to which key bodies related to the Government or otherwise that are tasked with enacting government policy in forestry and woodland such as the Forest Commission, Forestry and Land Scotland, Natural England or the Woodland Trust, for example, are considering and actualising natural capital approaches.

Using an inductive approach, we examined documents from a cross section of policy sectors and used the information gathered to perform a preliminary analysis on identified themes. Considering a broad range of policy topics has given us the opportunity to find out which policy areas have seen a take-up of natural capital concepts and to theorise why this might be. This overview has allowed a more holistic view on UK and Scottish government commitment to natural capital approaches.

- 1.2 Identification of Documents for Analysis

The approach taken to identifying documents for analysis was not systematic and as such a strict protocol for document identification was not drawn up. Documents have been identified for analysis through a process of snowballing, in which we first identified key natural capital instruments by conducting a key word search on 'natural capital' on both the HM Government and Scottish Government websites. From these documents we were able to identify another wave of relevant policy documents and grey literature for analysis, and so on. In addition, where key government-run bodies or independent bodies which enact policy or are regulated by it were highlighted as having an interest or stake in natural capital or in operationalising the policy itself, we followed these leads and included searches of their websites and collections of grey or policy literature within our analysis.

Once this process had been exhausted, we used the same snowballing approach to examine broad areas of policy, starting at the highest level and moving down through secondary policy. Sectors chosen for analysis were picked either due to a hunch that they might have some logical relationship with natural capital (e.g., the economic sector, for example, which has a natural link with accounting and processes of valuation) and / or because they have some propensity to impact on the management of trees, woodlands or forests (agricultural policy, for example, may impact upon the management of wooded areas on agricultural land). As such policy sectors chosen for analysis included climate change, planning and land use, agriculture, conservation and biodiversity, and economic contexts. Finally, the process was repeated in the area of forest policy itself as a key area of focus within our report.

Through inductive reasoning, documents or grey literature written prior to 2011 were rarely considered since it was only at this point that natural capital concepts started to be introduced. Policies and literature were skim read and key word searches for the term 'natural capital' were performed where possible to determine their relevance. If 'natural capital' did not produce results the search was broadened to include the term 'ecosystem services' since policies which consider or operationalise ecosystem services are closely related and an understanding and inclusion of one or both concepts may be necessary in order to operationalise natural capital.

Although in many instances, where there was no discussion of natural capital or ecosystem services, documents were excluded from the analysis, a number of key overarching policies which did not include any mention of natural capital or ecosystem services were kept in, since the fact of this lack of inclusion was of significant interest in itself. Likewise, within forest policy we have kept and noted

within our analysis key instances where natural capital or ecosystem services have not been discussed since one of our research aims was to explore which policy areas and types of instruments within these areas had included consideration of natural capital approaches and which had not.

In particular, in accordance with GGKP's classification criteria for assessing cases in their working paper of international 'Practical policy use cases for natural capital information' (2020) which we found particularly useful for its methodical approach to classifying types of government decisions within the policy field, we focused on searching for instances in which natural capital was made 'operational' (2020, p.6) or where 'regulatory' (2020, p.6) text had been instrumentalised. In addition, we applied the GGKP classification category of 'finance and investment' (2020, p.6) in cases where private investment was sought or where private sector involvement took place but did not include a full search of PES schemes, since only one was found in our initial searches using the method described above. The category also applies to financial support offerings for landowners or others implementing natural capital approaches on their land. For the 'technical' (2020, p.6) category we searched only for key knowledge-based tools and advice which was available from the government entities and related enacting bodies, which were already being analysed. This is because the field of technical tools available for working with natural capital, such as accounting or mapping tools for example, is huge and collating information on these was out of the scope of this report. The category of 'policy and planning' (2020, p.6) was not used since it refers to the ways in which policies 'organise' the integration of natural capital into other policies and plans. We felt such organisation of natural capital approaches fell more readily into alternative categories of operationalising or regulating. Where this was not the case, the remainder of cases in which natural capital approaches were discussed tended to be included as high-level concepts within both UK and Scottish policy. As such we added an extra classification of 'conceptual' decision making to cover this aspect.

- 1.3 Structure of the Report

Following the method logic described above, beginning with overarching UK policy and moving through Scottish policy, Chapter 2, which summarises the results of the search, explores whether, and how, natural capital principles are currently being applied and enacted in high level instruments, within different policy sectors, and then, specifically within forestry and woodland policy. It then moves on to outline current mechanisms and initiatives for supporting landowners to implement natural capital approaches within both the public and private spheres. We then move on within Chapter 3 to synthesise these results and discuss their implications. We have used the five research questions posed to outline the focus of each section of the chapter, addressing one question within each section. The exception to this are sections 3.31 and 3.32, which address the first two questions. As following the initial description of specific natural capital instruments in Chapter 2 (sections 2.11, 2.12, 2.13 and 2.14) it felt logical to consider each policy sector as a whole, by following through from high level to secondary policy within each area. Finally, we draw some conclusions on the extent to which natural capital is embedded in UK and Scottish policy and support mechanisms, the forms this takes, and the extent to which high level UK policy influences the Scottish policy context. We consider the extent to which, and the ways in which the private sector is involved in natural capital issues and make a broad set of recommendations for ways forward in these respects.

- 1.4 Descriptive Analysis of Reviewed Studies

This section provides some information on the number of analysed policies within several of categories. It is important to note that the approach taken to this report was not systematic or exhaustive and data has not been coded. Decisions on which data sources belonged in each category and on what a ‘tangible’ inclusion of natural capital approaches looked like were taken manually and are thus subjective. As such, the information is for interest only and it should not be assumed that it represents the sum-total of relevant data in the field. As ball-park figures, however, it is interesting to see the differences in proportional inclusions across, for example, the UK and Scotland, or across the policy categories.

The following table (Figure 1) indicates the number of policy data sources found for the UK and Scottish governments which include some tangible mention of natural capital concepts. This table excludes specific forest and woodland policy, which is found in Figure 2, and excludes public or private mechanisms for supporting landowners to operationalise natural capital (instruments which belong to GGKP’s ‘technical’ or ‘finance and investment’ categories). Although the UK shows a greater number of tangible inclusions of natural capital concepts within policy the difference is marginal. While steps are being taken to incorporate natural capital approaches across policy sectors, the small numbers overall indicate that there is still a long way to go before natural capital approaches are fully embedded within UK and Scottish policy.

Figure 1: Government data sources across policy sectors

UK	Scotland
18	10

Figure 2 shows the number of data sources found in UK and Scottish forest policy which include tangible mention of natural capital concepts. Here again the numbers are extremely minimal and indicate that little has yet been done in this regard within the sector.

Figure 2: Government data sources in forest policy

UK	Scotland
2	2

Figure 3: Government data sources across six policy sectors

UK					
Natural Capital	Planning and Land Use	Agriculture	Conservation and Biodiversity	Economic	Climate Change
5	2	1	2	6	2

Scotland					
Natural Capital	Planning and Land Use	Agriculture	Conservation and Biodiversity	Economic	Climate Change
2	2	0	2	3	1

Figure 3 shows data sources for the UK and Scotland across the five policy sectors analysed. In addition, since there is an emerging set of instruments related to natural capital itself, this has been included as a sixth policy sector. The table does not include technical or finance and investment instruments. For both the UK and Scotland it is clear that the bulk of work has focused on the emerging natural capital sector itself while other policy sectors, although showing some signs of activity, are not yet effectively incorporating natural capital approaches to any significant level. The following section explores the data sources to a deeper level by examining more closely the results of the data search.

CHAPTER 2: RESULTS

2.1 Natural Capital in Overarching Policy and Across Policy Sectors

This section summarises the results of data collection activities with respect to the extent to which natural capital approaches are incorporated into overarching and secondary policy. Beginning with the UK and then moving on to Scotland, for each nation it explores targeted natural capital instruments, and then moves through the five chosen policy sectors of climate change policy, planning and land use policy, agriculture policy, conservation and biodiversity policy, and economic and industrial policy.

- 2.11 Key Instruments in an Emerging Area of Focus on Natural Capital in the UK

The UK's first significant step towards using natural capital concepts in policy was the creation of the UK National Ecosystem Assessment (UKNEA, 2011), an examination of the state of the UK's ecosystem services and the changes occurring within them. It noted that the UK's ecosystems and the benefits they bestowed were undervalued and under-protected. Following the Millennium Assessment's system of classification, it grouped them into provisioning, regulation, cultural and support services and this categorisation system has largely remained in use across UK policy henceforth. Although not the focus of the UKNEA, the assessment laid the ground for future natural capital developments like the UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow On (UKNEAFO, 2014), which highlighted shared, plural and cultural values of ecosystem services, developed a conceptual framework for the analysis of cultural services and noted a need for systems of valuation capable of incorporating non-monetary values within or alongside economic accounts. It highlighted links between ecosystem services and economic impact and discussed the importance of, and barriers to, embedding ecosystem service concepts into policy decision making, developing 'Adaptive Management Principles' (p.6) to aid in this process. A Decision Support System Toolbox was developed for policy decision making alongside a Balance Sheet Approach for the collation and analysis of ecosystem service data. Importantly, the UKNEAFO called for natural capital values to be included in UK National Accounts.

From this grounding in ecosystem services concepts UK policy began to explore natural capital approaches, with the establishment of the Natural Capital Committee (NCC) in 2012 (Natural Capital Committee, 2022). An independent committee who advised the Government on natural capital related matters through until 2020, when its functions were largely devolved to the new Office for Environmental Protection, the NCC were a driving force behind the inclusion of natural capital considerations in the revised HM Treasury Green Book (2022).

Off the back of NCC recommendations HM Government's 25 Year Environment Plan (2018) states the UK's ambition to 'lead[...] the world in using... [a natural capital] approach as a tool in decision making' (p.9). Made legally binding via the Environment Act (HM Government, 2021 [2]), which contains an obligation to consider biodiversity net gain in policy making, the Plan describes an 'Outcome Indicator Framework' to measure environmental change, proposes the creation of the Office for Environmental Protection to monitor Government action on natural capital, the development of a set of assessment metrics, and the designation of Nature Recovery Networks in England to 'protect and restore wildlife' at a landscape scale (p.56). It describes intentions to establish a new Environmental Land Management Scheme (see section 2.31) alongside a number of natural capital Pioneer pilot projects (see Figure 4 below), a green business council to advise Government on private sector involvement in natural capital issues, the inclusion of requirements for environmental net gain in development planning and a future requirement for this net gain to extend to a wider range of ecosystem services such as flood protection etc. The Plan is written in the language of economic growth and benefits, and although it covers wellbeing benefits and social action, these are not explicitly linked to natural capital.

Figure 4: Pioneer Project Trials

A set of trials were set up by Defra with start dates ranging from 2017 to 2020 which link to the 25 Year Environment Plan (2018). These four pilot 'pioneer' projects in England which used natural capital approaches to decision making. These included: the North Devon Landscape Pioneer, which is using natural capital approaches to undertake valuation of ecosystem services, to prioritise action for the Biosphere Reserve, and to test a 'payment-by-results' (p.137) farming model; Cumbria Catchment Pioneer, wherein the Environment Agency is working with communities to test both natural capital approaches to the management of river catchments and a PES-style financing scheme for 'visitor-giving' (p.137); Greater Manchester Urban Pioneer, led by the Environment Agency in partnership with Greater Manchester Combined Authority which focuses on biodiversity net gain and on finding ways to improve local people's quality of life by enhancing natural capital; and the Marine Pioneer, led by the Marine Management Organisation in North Devon Biosphere and the Suffolk Coasts and Heaths Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty, which is undertaking a natural capital assessment of saltmarsh restoration and working with industry fisheries on sustainability plans. As-yet there are no public reports on the outcomes of these trials.

The Office for Environmental Protection (OEP) is a public body created under the Environment Act and in response to the 25 Year Plan (HM Government, 2018 [1]) to provide checks and balances to government (at the highest level but also for local authorities and even in some cases for some private bodies such as water companies) on environmental matters in England and Northern Ireland (2022). Its role includes inspection of and advising on environmental law and the inspection of environmental improvement plans, for example. Although the OEP states that it will continue the work of the NCC it is too early to tell whether working to include natural capital approaches in policy will form any significant part of its remit.

- 2.12 Natural Capital Approaches in Five UK Policy Sectors

This section moves on to consider the level to which natural capital approaches are incorporated and considered within economic, climate change, planning and land use, agriculture and conservation and biodiversity policy in the UK.

- *UK Economic Policy*

The Green Book is the Government's guidance for policy makers on policy appraisal and evaluation and uses the language of cost, benefit and risk to inform policy decision making. For the first time in 2018 it incorporated the recognition that consideration of non-market values within policy decision making was important for 'environmental, social and health effects' (p.58). The Green Book suggests a range of techniques for the estimation of non-market values such as, for example, revealed preference, social cost benefit analysis or evidence of wellbeing methods and recommends that natural capital assessment be carried out to measure and monitor policy effects.

'The Clean Growth Strategy: leading the way to a low carbon future' (HM Government, 2017 [3]), which aims to reduce emissions yet increase economic growth, includes recognition of natural capital impacts from economic policy, and the twin goals of increasing carbon capture and protecting natural capital. It highlights focuses on tree planting, forest creation and forestry investment, and on building up the carbon offset market. Also in 2017, the Government's 'Industrial Strategy: building a Britain fit for the future' (HM Government, 2017 [2]) stated an intent to enhance natural capital and target investments in areas, such as woodland planting, the restoration of peatland and creation of wetland areas. It is clearly stated that the thinking here reflects the idea that healthy, abundant natural capital leads to 'significant economic growth' (2017, 2, p.148).

Perhaps, the most interesting example comes from the Office for National Statistics (ONS). The ONS produces Environmental Accounts conforming to principles from the UN's System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) (2021, 1). The accounts measure how the environment and economy impact upon each other and can be used to inform policy and evaluate environmental impact. As part of the Environmental Accounts, the UK's Natural Capital Accounts contain 'crude average' data on the UK's ecosystem services and detail 'estimates of the financial and societal value of natural resources to people in the UK' (ONS, 2021). These are included as 'part of a wider move to better understand wealth' and are described by ONS as 'experimental' and incomplete (ONS, 2021, 1). Notably, these natural capital accounts, which contain data on 13 ecosystem services, and habitat accounts for 8 habitats, have since 2020 been included in the Blue Book (2021, 2), the UK's full set of economic accounts. The ONS 'Natural Capital Accounts Roadmap' (2022, 1) sets out plans to improve the accounts by including probable climate change impacts for 2024 and estimates of degradation to assets, improving 'spatial granularity', inclusion of socio-economic data and accessibility and relevance of data for households, neighbourhoods, local authorities, private sector and charities.

- *UK Climate Change Policy*

In the area of overarching climate change policy, HM Government's 'Net Zero Strategy: build back greener' (2021 [8]) focuses on emissions reductions through carbon budgeting and includes aims to enhance the UK's natural capital and understand positive and negative impacts of net zero policy upon it via screening questions constructed in line with Green Book recommendations. The Government's 'UK Climate Change risk assessment 2022' (HM Government, 2022, and Betts and Brown, 2021), the third five-yearly assessment of climate change risks in the UK undertaken with the UK's Climate Change Committee, utilises natural capital ideas in a more practical way, interweaving assessments of risk to natural capital throughout the report. The authors note that a comprehensive valuation of likely deterioration of natural capital as a result of climate change was not possible due to the speculative nature of future impacts.

- *UK Planning and Land Use Policy*

In 2020 The Committee on Climate Change published a paper 'Land Use: policies for a net zero UK', building on the Net Zero Strategy. The paper describes the huge scale of rapid land use change required to reach the UK's net zero target and discusses the need for the implementation of low-carbon practices, afforestation, agro-forestry, peatland restoration, bioenergy crops, a reduction in consumption of carbon-intensive foods, and the facilitation of stronger regulation and funding programmes. The paper recognises that the state of natural capital necessarily impacts upon productivity and that it is important to include non-market benefits (such as recreation, health benefits and ecosystem services) in valuations of nature. It goes on to estimate values for social, ecosystem services and carbon sequestration benefits for both broadleaf and conifer woodlands in the UK but does not explicitly call for others to, for example, create natural capital accounts to influence land use decision making.

Within the government's 'National Planning Policy Framework' (2021 [7], and Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021), however, there is little mention of natural capital other than to suggest its enhancement is 'considered' at catchment or landscape scales, and it is stressed that while economic, social and environmental objectives should be integrated throughout policy decision making and implementation 'they are not criteria against which every decision can or should be judged' (2021, 2).

Furthermore, policy tools for enacting environmental assessments, such as 'The Environmental Impact Assessment' (HM Government, 2017 [1]) and 'The Town and Country Planning (Environmental Impact Assessment)' (HM Government, 2017 [4]), do not include natural capital as elements that need to be assessed or considered in environmental statements or decision-making processes.

- *UK Agriculture Policy*

Within agriculture, the Agriculture Act (UK Parliament, 2020, and HM Government, 2020 [1], HM Government, 2020 [4]) grants the government powers to reform agricultural policy and payments following Brexit and contains no mention of natural capital. It does, however, state government

intention to phase out the Basic Payment Scheme under the Common Agricultural Policy (European Commission, 2022) and introduce payments under the Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS) for 'public goods', or in other words for the protection and enhancement of natural capital and ecosystem services for farmers. Further discussion of the ELMS can be found below in section 2.31.

- *UK Conservation and Biodiversity Policy*

As far back as 2012, the UK Government's Joint Nature Conservation Committee and Defra 'UK Post-2010 Biodiversity Framework' (2012) built on the UKNEA and aimed to identify, value and protect natural capital and address biodiversity loss across the UK. Its 'Revised Implementation Plan (2018-2020)' (JNCC and Defra, 2018) goes slightly further to include objectives to promote natural capital approaches through knowledge exchange and to engage with natural capital initiatives.

- 2.13 Key Instruments in an Emerging Area of Focus on Natural Capital in Scotland

This section will describe how natural capital ideas are being incorporated into Scottish policy thus far, beginning with explicit natural capital instruments and initiatives and moving through its inclusion in broader policy areas.

The Scottish Forum on Natural Capital was created in 2013 to engage public, private and voluntary sector stakeholders in discussion and action around the protection and enhancement of natural capital. Key steering group members include the Scottish Wildlife Trust, Scotland's 2020 Climate Group, the University of Edinburgh, the Institute of Chartered Accountants in Scotland, and the Institute of Directors Scotland. Its focus areas include impact via policy and legislation through support of the development of a Scottish natural capital policy framework that includes business incentives and penalties; impact via knowledge and innovation, through the facilitation of collaborative, cross-sectoral research into natural capital thinking; and impact via action, through support which facilitates organisational take-up of natural capital initiatives such as the Natural Capital Protocol (see section 2.31), and increases natural capital investment. The Forum provides access to natural capital tools and Small Action Learning Groups which focus collective attention and action on specific, place-based natural capital issues.

The Scottish Government's 'Interim Principles for responsible investment in natural capital' (2022 [2]) is intended as an outline for the building of a 'responsible' natural capital market for private investment. Its principles aim to deliver ethical 'economic transformation' within the context of a 'Just Transition' to net zero which recognises injustices built into the transition process and creates a more equal society (Just Transition Commission, 2022). They aspire to tackle climate change and biodiversity loss and generate long-term, shared benefits for public, private and community gain. They advise that investment decisions should be made collaboratively with early community engagement and with consideration of shared community management or ownership options. Carbon management investments should be verifiable via, for example, the Woodland Carbon Code (see section 2.32). Mention is made that impacts of investment and management decisions should be considered across 'all four capitals (natural, social, economic, human)'.

Within the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital four networks act as focused interest groups. The Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers, for example, aims to develop private investment pathways for

natural capital projects; the Sustainable Land Management Working Group promotes knowledge sharing around natural capital approaches in land management amongst public and private sector organisations; the Marine Natural Capital Forum Scotland enables collaborative discussions between technical and policy experts around marine capital; and ECom (Ecosystem Services Community) Scotland (2022) is a network interested in advancing collective, transdisciplinary understandings of ecosystem services to support Scottish policy- and decision-making and which brings together members across diverse public and private organisations. As of 2019 the ECom community spans over 600 researchers, decision-makers and practitioners who work together to create, share and align academic and practice-based knowledge, research and best practice, and who aim to achieve tangible impact in the field; while the ECom core membership team provides access to resources, runs events and provides spaces for debate and for the building of social networks, partnerships and mutual trust (Metzger et al, 2019). ECom is itself part of the oppla knowledge hub, an online community for sharing natural capital best-practice.

- 2.14 Natural Capital in Five Scottish Policy Sectors

This section describes the results of our search for inclusion of natural capital approaches in the Scottish economic, climate change, planning and land use, agriculture and conservation and biodiversity policy sectors.

- *Scottish Economic Policy*

The National Performance Framework (2022 [4&5]), which describes amongst key outcomes an ‘inclusive and sustainable economy’ and the protection and enhancement of the environment, incorporates natural capital as a National Indicator for economic success and tracks yearly changes in natural capital stock. Meanwhile ‘Scotland’s National Strategy for Economic Transformation’ (Scottish Government, 2022 [8]), employs an innovative nature-positive, wellbeing economy approach which views the restoration of natural capital as vital in shoring up economic productivity and job growth and creating new markets across multiple sectors. It describes the importance of encouraging responsible private investment into natural capital, a goal echoed in Scotland’s Programme for Government 2022-23 (Scottish Government, 2022), which lays out plans for the parliamentary term. This builds on the Programme for Scotland 2020-21 (Scottish Government, 2020 [2]) which in turn points out that Scotland’s economic recovery from covid must be a green one. Nature based investment features heavily in the programme, particularly around investment for forestry for new planting and for nursery capacity. It introduces the concept of a Green Investment Portfolio (see section 2.42 below) and discusses measures to booster land markets.

- *Scottish Climate Change Policy*

There is little on natural capital in policy instruments prior to 2018. More recent instruments such as the 'Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032: securing recovery on a path to net zero' (Scottish Government, 2020 [5]), are beginning to touch on natural capital concepts. The update discusses measures to rebuild a greener, more just economy as Scotland comes out of the pandemic. It describes natural capital as central to reducing emissions, creates a picture of future economies built around woodland creation, and again recognises the need for greater understanding of barriers to private investment into natural capital and innovative financing mechanisms.

- *Scottish Planning and Land Use Policy*

The Scottish Planning Policy (Scottish Government, 2020 [3]), which sits alongside the National Planning Framework, considers the importance of enhancing natural resources but goes no further. 'Land use – getting the best from our land: strategy 2021 to 2026' (Scottish Government, 2021 [1]) discusses both the Scottish Government's adoption in principle of the 'four capitals' for economic development (pp.10-11) and the need to enhance natural capital stocks in order to bolster the economy, health, wellbeing and air and water quality. It highlights government promotion of Ecosystem Approaches in land use and planning. It flags the Woodland Carbon Capture Investment Programme, which aims to boost private investment into natural capital via forestry and build a solid woodland carbon market and discusses government commitments for new forestry planting and for building nursery stocks. And further back, although the 'Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement' (Scottish Government, 2017 [1]) does not explicitly mention natural capital, there is a cross-over within concepts discussed around values or benefits to managing land sustainably, ethically and for the 'public good'. The statement discusses the importance of respecting and fulfilling human rights in relation to land, explores the concept of stewardship and seeks to involve communities in decision making around land. It also describes how well-managed and stewarded land can contribute to economic gain as well as offering social, cultural and environmental benefits.

- *Scottish Agriculture Policy*

The 'Scottish Rural Development Programme (SRDP)' (Scottish Government, 2022 [9]) is a government funding mechanism for the rural economy, agriculture and forestry in Scotland (discussed further below in section 2.32). It describes the importance of ecosystem services but does not introduce natural capital concepts. The transition to a new rural support policy in the wake of Brexit is discussed further in the Scottish Government paper 'Stability and simplicity: proposals for a rural funding transition period' (Scottish Government, 2018 [2]), however again, whilst discussion of ecosystem services is included, discussion of natural capital is not.

However, Scotland's vision for Scottish agriculture ('The next step in delivering our vision for Scotland as a leader in sustainable and regenerative farming', Scottish Government, 2022 [14]) notes that conditionality related to biodiversity gain and emissions reductions will become integral to 50% of agriculture funding schemes by 2025, describes a future focus on designing 'mechanisms to support outcomes that restore nature, benefit our natural capital and promote the natural economy' and

highlights that future land use change decisions will be facilitated from the perspective of natural capital and Just Transition approaches (Scottish Government, 2022 [14], p.2). A National Test Programme active from Spring 2022 will trial conditionality payments, the collection of data from farms around their baseline levels of 'environmental performance and efficiency' (Scottish Government, 2022 [14], p.6) and seeks to develop and test tools and guidance mechanisms to support farmers to implement policy changes.

NatureScot's (2022 [3]) 'Farming with Nature' programme has been set up to inform some of these changes to rural support mechanisms post CAP, featuring a series of pilot projects which highlight natural capital approaches. The pilots are guided by an external advisory group with members from the Nature Friendly Farming Network, the RSPB, the James Hutton Institute, the National Farmers Union of Scotland, the Scottish Association of Young Farmers Clubs, Scottish Land and Estates, the Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust Scotland, and the Scottish Crofting Federation. They include a project entitled 'Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach in Scotland' (POBAS), a component of Scotland's National Test Programme, designed to test 'natural capital and outcomes-based approaches to inform future rural policy' (NatureScot, 2022 [4]). With 80 farmers and crofters based on a variety of farm types, operating in clusters across Scotland, POBAS uses results-based payments to incentivise positive natural capital outcomes via the use of habitat scorecards. Alongside this sits work supported by the Scottish Government's CivTech programme, featuring a digital natural capital app designed with tech company Icen. The app is intended to help farmers visualise, collect data on, and manage, natural capital on their land (NatureScot, 2022 [5]), while data collected will be uploaded directly to a central NatureScot platform for analysis (NatureScot, 2022 [4]). A project to develop and test on the ground a National Capital Assessment Template is also being piloted to support farmers and land-based businesses to undertake natural capital assessments. The template was produced by Cumulus Consultants Ltd and is designed based on evidence from the Natural Capital Protocol (NatureScot, 2022 [5]). NatureScot have also produced a literature review exploring the topic of 'facilitating local natural capital investment' to feed into a pilot co-managed by the Tweed Forum on supporting regional partnerships to achieve private investment into natural capital projects (NatureScot, 2022 [6]). Finally, mention is made of a test of natural capital approaches at landscape scale, but further details are not available. Pilots are intended to support post-covid economic recovery and the construction of an ethical wellbeing economy.

Furthermore, currently in their trial phase (see Figure 5 below) Regional Land Use Partnerships (RLUPs) bring together government at local and national levels with 'communities, land owners, land managers, and wider stakeholders' (Scottish Government, 2022 [13]). Stemming from commitments in the 2019 Programme for Government (Scottish Government, 2019 [3]) these partnerships will work collaboratively on land use changes in order to achieve net zero targets and are expected to be a suitable vehicle for operationalising landscape scale natural capital approaches. They are intended to provide opportunities for local engagement and empowerment in decision making around land use and to feed into government efforts to facilitate a high-integrity 'Just Transition' (Just Transition Commission, 2022) through innovative inclusive forms of governance.

From 2023 these will be developed into wider Regional Land Use Frameworks capable of working with natural capital approaches holistically at landscape scale. They are referenced as key to addressing biodiversity loss and climate change in the government's Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032 (Scottish Government, 2020 [5]) and feature as a key 'Platform for Change' in 'Scotland's Third Land Use Strategy 2021-2026: Getting the best from our land' (Scottish Government, 2021 [2])

Figure 5: Regional Land Use Partnership Trials

The Scottish Government (Scottish Government, 2021, Scottish Land and Estates, 2021), based on initial advice from the Scottish Land Commission (2019), is currently running a number of Regional Land Use Partnership (RLUP) pilot groups to test collaborative land governance and natural capital approaches across a diverse set of landscapes and natural capital types with the Cairngorms National Park, the Highland Council, Loch Lomond and the Trossachs National Park, and Dumfries and Galloway Council. Two early trials in 2016 (Scottish Government, 2016 [2]) tested the practicality of the approach in Aberdeenshire and the Scottish Borders and are now closed. They found the approach to be challenging and complex but were cautiously optimistic about their potential. The early stages of the current pilot projects, meanwhile, focused on identifying key stakeholders and scoping approaches to natural capital through consultation events. In the second phase which runs from 2023, the Cairngorms, Loch Lomond and Trossachs, North East and South of Scotland projects will be extended. This stage will test approaches to governance, stakeholder engagement, and data and natural capital, amongst other things (World Bank Group, SRUC, Scottish Government, South of Scotland Enterprise, BioCarbon Fund, 2022). Few findings have been released so far but Scottish Land and Estates has noted the importance of suitable tools for land management and clarity around working practices for RLUP success.

- *Scottish Conservation and Biodiversity Policy*

In terms of conservation and biodiversity, as far back as 2015 'Scotland's Biodiversity: a route map to 2020' (Scottish Government) discussed the need to enhance natural capital, highlighted a problematic lack of 'recognition of the value of nature' within decision making and outlined Scottish Government aims to invest in understanding and protecting natural capital through the restoration of ecosystem services, the engagement of businesses in understanding their dependencies and impact upon natural capital through the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital, a focus on citizen science to increase capacity for data collection and raise awareness around natural capital benefits, and the development of the Natural Capital Asset Index, a natural capital account which measures the quality and quantity of habitats and their 'potential to deliver ecosystem services' (Scottish Government, 2022). As expected, older policy documents such as the Scottish Government's 'Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act 2004' for the provision of policy for biodiversity protection and conservation make no mention of natural capital.

2.2 Natural Capital in Forest Policy

This section will go on to examine the use of natural capital concepts within high level forest and woodland policy, beginning with the UK. We will then examine the extent to which the UK's overarching forest policy is instrumentalised in second level policy; since this is largely devolved, we have included English forest / woodland policy here. We then move on to look at Scottish forest and woodland policy in the same manner.

- 2.21 UK Forest Policy

Key to UK forestry policy is 'The UK Forestry Standard. The government's approach to sustainable forestry' (Forestry Commission, 2017). The UKFS informs forestry policy and its implementation across England and the devolved governments of Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland and facilitates the delivery of international forest management agreements. Although the UKFS recognises equitable, integrated ecosystem approaches which encompass social, cultural and economic factors, as-yet it appears that it has not been updated with natural capital perspectives beyond the recognition of natural assets as 'natural capital'.

However, the Science and Innovation Strategy for Forestry in Great Britain (Welsh Government, Defra, Scottish Forestry, and Forestry Commission, 2020) provides a more comprehensive incorporation of natural capital ideas which are threaded throughout, with natural capital accounting described as relevant to 'monitoring progress towards environmental goals' (p.9). The strategy, overseen by the Welsh Government, focuses on priority research areas across all four nations which contribute to the increase of natural capital, mitigation of climate change and protection and enhancement of biodiversity via the facilitation of applied research and evidence gathering to feed into policy, regulation, and practice. Research is intended to be transdisciplinary, with contributions sought from researchers, policymakers, forestry practitioners, communities of interest and wider society (p.25). Key research areas include, amongst others, 'sustainable forest management' to support economic growth (p.17); 'markets for forest products and services', including the development of research around Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) (p.18); 'societal benefits from trees, woods and forests' including research around valuing tree/ forest-based solutions for improved health and wellbeing (p.19); 'Resource assessment and sector monitoring', including improved data acquisition, modelling and trend monitoring (p.20); 'achieving multiple ecosystem benefits', including valuing and promoting the range of benefits and monitoring and valuing changes in them and improving the 'design of finance mechanisms to achieve multiple benefits' including research which informs the design of government grants and funding for forestry projects (p.21); and 'woodland creation and expansion' to increase tree cover (p.22). Broader aims include the facilitation of knowledge exchange, capacity building, partnership building, the development of new methods of data collection and analysis and greater engagement with end users, and it includes aims to provide evidence of the economic benefits of forests and to inform public and private investment in forestry. Its role is described as 'Adding to the published evidence underpinning the UK Forestry Standard and its supporting suite of guidance' (p.26).

In terms of regulatory instruments (including regulations on tree felling and preservation, tree and plant health, the protection of woodland wildlife, and the importing and exporting of timber and forest products (HM Government, 2020, 2021 [1], 2021 [5], 2021 [6], 2022)) these are devolved and for

England there are none which include the requirement for woodland or forest owners to use natural capital approaches. Environmental Impact Assessments for Woodlands (HM Government, 2021 [4]) for afforestation, deforestation, forest road and forest quarry projects also lack any impetus for the consideration of natural capital approaches.

Defra's 'England Trees Action Plan 2021 to 2024' (2021 [5]), notes the financial value of England's woodlands for timber, the existence of ecosystem services and natural capital, and an aim to increase 'green finance for trees and woodlands' (p.7). Beyond this, natural capital concepts are not discussed. Defra's 'Keepers of time' paper on the protection of ancient and native woodland (2022 [1]), discusses the great value of ancient trees and the soils they are sited in as natural capital, as carbon stores and as cultural, health and wellbeing resources. It commits to facilitating understanding of ecosystem services, working to increase private investment in ancient and native woodlands and new markets for sustainable timber and other forest products, and more broadly to protecting and enhancing them. Information on how this will be carried out or any form of regulatory mechanism is not included.

A 2022 guidance document from Natural England and the Forestry Commission on making planning decisions around ancient and veteran trees and woodlands does not mention natural capital at all, although it does note their value across many different areas including for biodiversity, recreation, health and cultural reasons. It calls for mitigation or compensation measures or buffer zones to be actioned by developers but describes the importance of protecting ancient woodlands and trees in planning decisions as to be decided 'on a case-by-case basis' and with reference to the National Planning Policy Framework which, as we have seen (in section 2.12), does not in itself oblige anything more than a 'consideration' of the protection of natural capital. Furthermore, Defra's Trees and Woodland Science Advisory Group (2021 [3]) does not appear to be publicly engaged in natural capital approaches and the Forestry Commission's 'Managing England's woodlands in a climate emergency' (2020) does not reference the concept of natural capital at all.

- 2.22 Scottish Forest Policy

By 2017, while some policies in other sectors in the UK (such as the Clean Growth Strategy, 2017 [3]) were starting to include natural capital concepts, 'The Forestry (Environmental Impact Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations 2017' (Scottish Government, 2017 [2]) neglected to include any explicit requirements to consider the natural capital impacts of forestry projects, although impacts upon, for example, human health, land, soil, water, air and climate are considered. In addition, the 'Forestry and Land Management (Scotland) Act 2018' (Scottish Government, 2018 [1]) which completes the devolution of forestry governance to Scotland, does not touch on natural capital or ecosystem services approaches. Under it, Scottish Ministers must make provision for 'sustainable forest management', woodland creation, conservation, the 'economic development of forestry' and the 'social benefits of forestry'.

From 2019, some small nods towards the existence of natural capital approaches start to show up in Scottish forestry policy. 'Scotland's Forestry Strategy: 2019-2029 overview' (Scottish Government, 2019 [2]) emphasises the economic contribution of forestry, not just through forest product markets but also through tourism and recreation. More recently, 'Scotland's Forestry Strategy Implementation Plan: 2022-2025' (Scottish Government, 2022 [7]) discusses natural capital at a similarly conceptual level, neglecting to explain how these approaches will be used or enforced in practice. It draws links with the Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital and highlights government

ambitions for a ‘values-led, high-integrity market for responsible investment in natural capital’. Amongst a wide range of strategies being implemented for the shoring up of forest and woodland spaces, woodland creation, protection of Scotland’s rainforests, natural regeneration projects, the inclusion of deliberative processes in decision making, community wealth building and research and the rolling out of projects which highlight the wellbeing and (mental) health benefits stemming from forests and woodlands all feature.

Furthermore, Forestry and Land Scotland (FLS), one of two bodies alongside Scottish Forestry who enact Scottish forestry policy on behalf of the government, developed a new strategic approach to land (and therefore forest) acquisition in 2021. The change provides opportunities for FLS to acquire land that can ‘deliver Natural Capital benefits such as peatland restoration, [and] flood alleviation’. Funding streams will be utilised, amongst other things, to acquire new land for afforestation, restoration and re-greening in contribution to carbon capture, biodiversity enhancement and to the UK’s net zero strategy. Again, we can see that methods of operationalising natural capital approaches are missing from the strategy.

Looking beyond Scottish Government policy, there are a number of other organisations which enact forestry and woodland policy in Scotland, however as-yet natural capital concepts do not seem to have trickled down to them. The Woodland Trust Scotland (2022), for example, which manages 11,000 hectares of woodland in Scotland, does not currently appear to be publicly engaged with natural capital ideas at all. Perhaps more promisingly, the Alliance for Scotland’s Rainforest (2022) is a voluntary partnership of organisations which works to protect and enhance Scottish rainforests. Although they are not currently using natural capital approaches, case studies show they are beginning to focus on landscape-scale projects which highlight and strengthen ecosystem services.

2.3 Public Technical and Finance Mechanisms for Supporting Landowners with Natural Capital Approaches

As we have seen, the UK and Scottish governments, while both largely still at the stage of conceptualising natural capital concepts within policy material, are cautiously leaning towards operationalising and regulating policy instruments within certain sectors. This leads to the question of what measures of support are in place for landowners who may in the future be expected to implement these changes on the ground. This section explores measures which fall into GGKP’s (2020) government decision making typology categories of ‘technical’ and ‘finance’ (the investment part of this category is more usefully considered in section 2.4 on private sector involvement in natural capital approaches). This section will explore what, if any public mechanisms are available within these categories, beginning with the UK (including key mechanisms from England) and then moving on to Scotland.

- 2.31 UK Support Mechanisms

At the UK level, public mechanisms are primarily focused around financially-based support, as seen in the government's Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS) (HM Government, 2021 [3]), a Payment by Results (PbR) programme. This replaces the Rural Development Programme (RDP) (2022 [2]), an England-based scheme for agricultural funding which is coming to a close as a consequence of Brexit and its links to the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The ELMS enacts goals from the 25 Year Environment Plan through the facilitation of three schemes. In contrast to the RDP, wherein subsidies were paid according to the area of land managed, the ELMS will award payments as a reward for the fulfilment of environmental obligations. ELMS encompasses three incentive schemes. Under the Sustainable Farming Incentive, which launches in 2022 after a pilot in 2021, farmers choose between a set of standards to apply. The Local Nature Recovery scheme (Defra, 2021 [6]), which will launch in 2024 after a pilot beginning in 2022, subsidises farmers who support local nature recovery, and the Landscape Recovery scheme which pilots in 2022 and launches in 2024 will pay farmers for landscape and ecosystem recovery projects such as 'large-scale tree planting'. Meanwhile, whilst the ELMS is being rolled out, Countryside Stewardship funds under the RDP (HM Government, 2020 [2], Rural Payments Agency, 2021 [1, 2, 3 & 4]) are one of the few rural payment options currently still

Figure 6: ELMS Trials

In the UK, the Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS) has been a key focus of natural capital trials (HM Government, 2021 [3]). Under Defra's 'test and trials', around 80 farms and other land owning organisations developed natural capital accounts and 'Land Management Plans' (LMPs) that put the insights of the accounts into practice. Defra's report (2021 [7]) finds the LMPs and the guidance that comes with them to be a useful element of ELMS. Highlights from the results of the trials include that working at a landscape or county scale was important but difficult to achieve while expert and peer-to-peer or farm cluster advice from trusted advisors was found to be a key driver to land management change and there were calls for it to be integrated into ELMS funding. How to set payment rates attractive enough to incentivise action is still a matter for deliberation - the Income Forgone plus Costs approach was found to be insufficient whereas a natural capital payment approach was found to be inaccurate due to difficulties in reliably valuing natural capital in practice, for example within the Cornwall AONB (Cornwall AONB, 2022) and Clinton Devon Estates trials. Points-based approaches were applied within the Sustainable Farming Incentive scheme trial which appeared to work well. Simple interventions were financed effectively by some using reverse auctions. The National Trust successfully tested a natural capital assessment and natural capital accounts were tested in a number of trials and found to be useful for understanding baselines. Cultural benefits were found to be hard to value by Exmoor National Park Authority and the Barningham trial tested a cost-benefit analysis tool to decide between potential natural capital interventions, but its use for valuing changes in habitat condition and land management was found to be limited.

open to farmers, woodland owners, foresters and other land managers. These will phase out by 2024 to be replaced by the ELMS. They provide financial incentives for good management of the environment and include a few options for woodland management and creation under the scheme but are not intended to support the implementation of natural capital approaches. Various trials have taken place (see Figure 6)

Alongside this, the UK's key technical guidance and information offering, although accessible to all landowners in the devolved nations, is an English initiative from Defra.

ENCA ('Enabling a Natural Capital Approach', Defra, 2021 [4]) is a suite of knowledge- and tool-based components intended to sit alongside Green Book guidance to inform decision making for policymakers, public sector, private sector and third sector organisations. Although not catering

directly for landowners much of what is there, particularly within the guidance section, provides useful knowledge on natural capital and the ecosystem services it provides. The suite includes instruments for conducting risk assessments and CBA assessments, guides on monetising benefits, and information on natural capital accounting and spatial mapping. It promotes the UKNEAFO 'Balance Sheet Approach' (2014) (see section 2.1) but recognises that 'the focus on costs and benefits rather than ethics and meaning is a limitation of valuation' (2021). As such it recommends the use of qualitative and specifically deliberative methods and 'social and cultural assessment' (2021) to be carried out in tandem. Alongside the guidance contribution the ENCA Services Databook (Defra, 2021 [3]) and ENCA Services Asset Databook (Defra, 2021 [1]) assemble economic valuations of ecosystem services and their impacts, plus 'data sources, tools and studies'.

In the English forest policy sector financial support is available for woodland creation and tree planting for local authorities through the Woodland Creator Accelerator Fund (Forestry Commission, 2022) while the England Woodland Creation Offer allocates funding of up to £10,000 per hectare for new woodland planting, both through the Forestry Commission (2022). Neither fund has requirements for natural capital approaches to be used by applicants. Technical support for operationalising natural capital in the sector is lacking; information on how to put together a woodland management plan (HM Government, 2018), for example, which includes template plans, woodland maps and inventory templates and map-based tools, does not identify a requirement for natural capital approaches.

Beyond specific government policy key independent bodies produce a number of useful technical support measures. The British Standards Institution, for example, offers the BS 8632 standard for measuring natural capital stock changes, a set of minimum requirements for natural capital accounting (British Standards Institution, 2021).

Also, in the category of technical support sits the Natural Capital Protocol, a standardised 'decision making framework' for the identification, measurement and valuation of 'impacts and dependencies on natural capital' (Capitals Coalition, 2021) created by the Capitals Coalition, a UK-based global coalition working on advancing capital approaches. It exists alongside both Social and Human Capital protocols. In relation to forests, an offshoot of the Natural Capital Protocol, 'The Natural Capital Protocol: Forest Products Sector Guide' (Natural Capital Coalition, 2018) provides a useful discussion on and standardised framework for natural capital measurement and valuation specific to the forest product sector. Developed through stakeholder collaboration and public consultation and trialled in 2021 (see Figure 7), the guide recognises a range of positive and negative social impacts from the sector along the value chain and describes iterative steps required for natural capital assessment, including how to prepare for an assessment, identify relevant stakeholders, determine and measure impacts and dependencies, measure changes, make valuations, interpret and act on results and more broadly, how to 'make natural capital assessments part of how you do business' (p.64).

Figure 7: Forest Products Sector Guide of the Natural Capital Protocol Trial

A study commissioned by Scottish Forestry, Tilhill and SEPA and carried out by AECOM, RDI Associates and Cumulus Consultants in 2021 provided evidence that planting new woodlands increases the benefits of natural capital. A natural capital assessment was carried out based on the Forest Products Sector Guide of the Natural Capital Protocol in 2018 with the aim of testing the applicability of the Protocol for land-based businesses, to promote its use and to develop practical guidelines for its application. Findings showed that the Protocol could certainly be used in this context, provided a framework for businesses to operationalise natural capital approaches, and was useful for improving understanding of natural capital and ecosystem services, 'business dependencies and impacts and broader benefits to society' (p.1). However, challenges existed in several areas such as around 'integrating the business overview and generic assessment, gauging the most useful impacts to assess, and obtaining data' (p.1) and suggestions for improvement included the creation of a series of natural capital metrics. Values for the next 50 years were extrapolated and found to total around £20 million in today's prices (Farm Advisory Service, 2021, 4).

Finally, the UK Woodland Assurance Standard (UKWAS, 2022) and the FSC Standards (FSC, 2022), which provide certifiable standards for woodland management in the UK also lack any inclusion of natural capital thinking. Nevertheless, the UKWAS describes the need for new woodlands to be designed with a view to facilitating the delivery of ecosystem services and requires recognition of the social benefits of woodlands, and the FSC (2022), provides opportunities for certified ecosystem services stewardship claims. The FSC Global Strategy for 2021 (2020) states that forests 'must be treasured for the value and benefits they provide... Resilient forests embody the true economic, social and environmental value of forests' (2020, p.5) and indeed one key goal is to increase 'awareness of the value of forests' (p.19).

- 2.32 Scottish Support Mechanisms

In the category of financial support, the 'Scottish Rural Development Programme (SRDP)' (Scottish Government, 2022 [9]) is a government funding mechanism for the rural economy, agriculture and forestry in Scotland. It describes the importance of ecosystem services to the forestry sector. Under the Programme lie a number of different schemes. The Agri-Environment Climate Scheme (Scottish Government, 2022), delivered with the Inspections Division and NatureScot and running until 2024, promotes land management approaches which improve water quality and manage flood risk amongst other things. The Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Fund (Scottish Government, 2022 [3]) promotes agricultural knowledge transfer and collaboration around topics including environmental performance and sustainability via training, coaching, workshops, courses and farm visits.

The Scottish Rural Network (Scottish Government, 2022 [10]) funds projects which include knowledge sharing around innovative practices in agriculture and forestry. Additionally, under a new National Test Programme the 'Preparing for Sustainable Farming' fund (2022 [6]) will act as an incentive for farmers to carry out biodiversity gain and emissions reductions projects as a condition for receiving agricultural support. Other Scottish government funding options for landowners such as the Crofting Agricultural Grant Scheme (2022), the Small Farms Grant Scheme' (2022 [11]), the Sustainable Agriculture Capital Grant Scheme (2022 [12]) and the Woodland Grazing grant (2022 [1]) do not appear suitable for incentivising practical natural capital approaches.

Within the forestry sector, the Scottish Government's 'Forestry Grant Scheme' (2022) offers a selection of options for funding, including for new woodland creation where it provides 'economic, environmental and social benefits', or protects soil and water, for example. However, neither it, nor the Forestry Co-operation grant (Scottish Government, 2017) which offers funding for 'landscape scale projects involving a number of landowners', specifically incentivises natural capital approaches. From Scottish Forestry, the 'Community Fund' (2022) which awards grants to community groups, voluntary groups, development trusts, social enterprises, charities and local authorities for projects that include communities in decision making around woodlands and for valuations that are related to Community Asset Transfer Schemes, also neglects to fund natural capital projects within its remit. Likewise, the Small Woodland Loan Scheme (Scottish Forestry, 2022 [4]) which provides loan-based funding up to £40,000 for the costs of application to the Forestry Grant Scheme for new woodland planting.

Beyond government-based or enacting body forestry funding schemes, several options for funding forest or woodland projects exist, none of which currently explicitly include natural capital projects within their criteria. Future Woodlands Scotland are a charity working in the area of woodland creation and conservation (2022, 4). Their Research and Innovation grant scheme (2022, 3) awards up to £10,000 for applicants who evidence that their project benefits native Scottish woodlands. Alongside this, their Future Woodlands Fund (2022, 1) offers funding options for Forestry Grant Scheme applications and Woodland Carbon Code applications, including for the creation of new woodlands, for carbon ownership and for the regeneration of derelict woodland areas. There is also at least one example of a locally-based funding source; the Borders Forest Trust 'Woodland Creation Advisory Service' (2022) works with landowners, businesses, farmers and community groups to restore native woodlands through the provision of advice, site surveys, support around woodland design and support to access funding. Grants of up to £1,000 are available for planting small groups of trees as is financial support for the preparation of applications to the Forestry Grant Scheme.

Other opportunities for funding include the National Lottery's 'Awards for All Scotland' (2022) and 'Scottish Land Fund' (2022), wherein applicants are required to demonstrate a community angle to their projects and either improve important spaces within the community or achieve 'more sustainable economic, environmental and / or social development through ownership of land...'. Finally, the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (2022) offers funding for projects found within 10 miles of a landfill site which contain elements of land restoration or reclamation for environmental purposes, or the conservation or enhancement of biodiversity, amongst other criteria. It is possible that a natural capital project may fall within the remit for funding here.

In the area of technical support mechanisms, the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital provides tools including support for natural capital project management, for encouraging board members to embed natural capital perspectives within organisational culture, and an 'ask an expert' online option. Furthermore, the Scottish Land Commission have created a protocol for landowners, managers, advisers and organisations related to land-use which includes natural capital management ('Land rights and responsibilities protocols: responsible natural capital and carbon management', 2022). It incorporates principles from the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement and the Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital to protect and enhance natural capital, to include community consultation in decision making, and to assess and monitor natural capital.

In addition, as part of the Scottish Rural Development Programme the government funds the Farm Advisory Service (2022, 1, Scottish Government, 2022 [1]), an information hub which aims to help farmers and crofters increase profits and sustainability. It offers knowledge exchange events, subscriptions, a telephone advice line, tools, apps and advice. It provides an online magazine covering farm woodland, a podcast on natural capital and how to manage it to maximise benefits for agriculture

and the rural economy (2022, 3), and videos which include, for example, case studies on farms where natural capital assessments have taken place (2022, 5) Alongside this it also offers some financial support, providing up to £1,200 funding for consultation advice on Integrated Land Management Plans, which lay out future farm or croft plans in a step by step guide and identify ‘opportunities and cost savings’, and up to £1,000 for specialist advice on maximising value through woodland or landscape management or woodland creation (2022, 2).

Two smaller resources also exist which explicitly aim to educate on, and operationalise, natural capital approaches: NatureScot has produced a series of short videos introducing the concept of natural capital for landowners (2022) and a guide to ‘Principles for Natural Capital Accounting on Public Land in Scotland’ (2021), which talks through the key technical and project management steps involved for best-practice in creating natural capital accounts; and Scottish Land & Estates report occasional news items related to natural capital (2021) and produce a podcast for landowners which touches on natural capital matters at times (2022). Finally, the Scottish Community Alliance’s ‘Community Learning Exchange’ (2022) is an online or in-person opportunity for communities to learn from one another’s experiences working on community projects and ventures. It is intended that opportunities to engage will shortly be extended to the Scottish Community Councils. It does not currently mention natural capital but could provide an opportunity for knowledge exchange in this regard.

Within the forestry sector, a new networking vehicle from Scottish Forestry and Scottish Government, the ‘Integrating Trees Network’ (2022), for farmers and crofters in Scotland aims to host knowledge-sharing events about tree-planting. The website includes a podcast on agro-forestry, interviews with peers, case studies, guides to funding applications for tree planting grants, and links to further advice and guidance. Currently it does not touch on natural capital approaches.

In the area of certification, the UK Woodland Carbon Code (2022) is an internationally recognised quality assurance standard which provides carbon rights for UK woodlands. Although this is a UK code it is managed by Scottish Forestry on behalf of England’s Forestry Commission and the UK’s other devolved forestry bodies. To align with the Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital, the code has been recently ‘strengthened’ through the revision of ‘additionality tests’ which provide more standardised, enhanced testing for the verification of carbon credits (Scottish Forestry, 2022 [3]).

Amongst non-government initiatives there is currently nothing to support the technical application of natural capital approaches. Examples include: the Community Woodlands Association, which has been supporting community groups to manage woodlands in Scotland since 2003 through the provision of training and networking opportunities; the Soil Association Scotland ‘Agroforestry’ offering (2022); and the Woodlands Trust ‘Croft Woodlands’ advisory team, which provides free advice on woodland planting and management to ‘crofters, smallholders and common grazings’ (2022) and offer funding for the costs of Forestry Grant Scheme applications. Natural capital approaches are not discussed by any of these bodies.

2.4 Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches

Alongside public sector efforts to find ways of operationalising natural capital approaches there is a parallel strand of thought and action occurring which is related to the private sector. This section collates the data on key efforts in the UK and then in Scotland.

- What level of involvement does the private sector have in natural capital approaches and how is this facilitated?
- 2.41 Private Sector Involvement in the UK

Examples of private sector initiated involvement (categorised as finance and investment) in natural capital approaches are collated in **Appendix 1** and include: four private sector initiated schemes which facilitated trading of services for the protection of natural assets (Capitals Coalition, 2022; EnTrade, 2022; LENS, 2022; and Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017); a number of UK government ELMS trials which include blended finance options and reverse auctions (Defra, 2021); a prospectus of investment projects from the Forestry Commission (Defra, 2021); government grant funding via the Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund (Environment Agency, 2022); an advisory council to Defra, the Council of Sustainable Business (Council for Sustainable Business, 2022 and HM Government, 2022 [1]); three local authority initiated projects (Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017; and Rivers Trust, 2022) and an example of paid service provision (Strutt and Parker, 2020).

- 2.42 Private Sector Involvement in Scotland

For Scotland examples that fall in the ‘finance and investment’ category of private sector involvement in natural capital approaches in Scotland are collated in **Appendix 2**. These include: the Scottish Government’s Green Investment Portfolio (2020 [1]); a SEPA and Scottish Wildlife Trust led collaborative partnership to plan private investment in Scotland via the Route Map to £1 Billion (SEPA and Scottish Wildlife Trust, 2020); the Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers and their work with CivTech, the Scottish Government, NatureScot and the Scottish Wildlife Trust on creating a new investment market for biodiversity credits; quality assurance schemes the UK Woodland Carbon Code and the IUCN UK Peatland Code; a research project from the Scottish Environment Protection Agency and the University of Edinburgh (Scottish Environment Protection Agency, University of Edinburgh); an example of paid service provision (Scottish Woodlands, 2022) and an organisation offering philanthropic funding (Baillie Gifford, 2022).

CHAPTER 3: SYNTHESIS AND DISCUSSION

This section draws together and discusses the results from the data search against the following research questions:

- To what extent and in what ways are natural capital approaches conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in overarching policy?
- To what extent are natural capital concepts conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in secondary policy?

3.31 Natural Capital in High Level and Secondary Policy Across Selected UK Policy Sectors

It is clear that since 2011 the UK has been exploring ideas related to ecosystem services and natural capital and how these might be brought into policy via the development of conceptual frameworks and early tools for policy decision making and natural capital accounting. However, it was not until 2018 that natural capital approaches were brought into legally binding environmental policy with the 25 Year Environment Plan (2018), through which natural capital concepts found marginal levers into environmental, conservation and biodiversity policy. While the establishment of the Natural Capital Committee (2022) signalled more than a passing interest in operationalising natural capital, since the passing of its duties to the Office for Environmental Protection it remains to be seen whether this focus on natural capital will wither or grow. If the former, the OEP's strategic objective to enforce compliance with environmental law might make it a powerful tool for compelling action against future natural capital regulatory instruments.

Despite the high level, conceptual nature of the 25 Year Environmental Plan it has prompted government departments and the public bodies that enact policy to begin to introduce natural capital and ecosystem services approaches into a wider range of policy instruments. These very recent developments are positive steps forward and although few provide any impetus to actually operationalise natural capital approaches they do introduce technical advice to improve understanding of policy impacts in the sector.

As yet UK conservation and biodiversity policy contains only vague conceptual inclusion of natural capital approaches while within climate change policy inclusion of natural capital approaches remains conceptual although inclusion and analysis of natural capital data within the Government's 'UK Climate Change Risk Assessment 2022' (HM Government, 2022; Betts and Brown, 2021) highlights a purposeful drive towards operationalising natural capital at least from government climate advisors.

Within planning and land use policy the introduction of natural capital concepts also appears to be moving cautiously with few instruments pertaining to natural capital. Of those that do, all mention remains conceptual rather than regulatory or operational, although it is interesting that discussion in, for example 'Land use – getting the best from our land: strategy 2021 to 2026' (Scottish Government, 2021) focuses attention on the four capitals approach, as such going further than instruments in other sectors to consider alternative conceptions of valuation. Although the 'National Planning Policy Framework' (2021 [7], and Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2021) would

seem to present an excellent opportunity for operationalising natural capital, by presenting natural capital approaches as optional rather than obligatory the government stops short of actualising the protection or enhancement of natural capital and as such this cannot be considered a regulatory instrument. Likewise, the various environmental impact assessments analysed which also lack any regulatory or operationalising function in this regard would seem to be missed opportunities for instrumentalising natural capital approaches on the ground and it will be interesting to see whether reforms which incorporate them will be attempted in the coming years.

Natural capital incorporation into agricultural policy is focused around the introduction of the Environmental Land Management Scheme, which provides operational leverage at ground level for natural capital approaches. Beyond this there is little to report in terms of any conceptual or otherwise inclusion in agricultural or rural development policy but it will be interesting to see whether and how this might follow suit once the ELMS gets underway.

It is in economic policy where the most interesting conceptual developments appear to be taking place. Whilst providing no regulatory or operational impact, the drawing of linkages between natural capital and economic growth in the Clean Growth (HM Government, 2017) and Industrial Strategies (HM Government, 2017) indicates a more fundamental change in economic thinking is beginning in this sector. This becomes more evident in consideration of the Office of National Statistics who, in response to the Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]), plan to include measures of inclusive wealth (see 'New beyond GDP measures for the UK', 2022, 2) in their accounting. With the aim to include 'measures of flows and benefits arising from capitals', including human capital, measures of 'Gross Inclusive Income' and 'Net Inclusive Income' will be included by 2023 and 2025 respectively. The feasibility of the inclusion of 'accounting' or 'shadow prices' is currently being explored, and, more broadly, ONS aims to challenge the view that wellbeing cannot be measured economically.

Furthermore, the inclusion of non-market values in the Green Book is seen as something of a victory by the Natural Capital committee (2020) in that it indicates a willingness to consider change at the highest level across all policy sectors, if not for all four capitals, at least for natural capital itself. Importantly, however, using a natural capital framework to appraise policy here is described as an 'option' alongside other environmental assessment methods (p.63). The policy maker is under no explicit obligation to undertake natural capital assessment, according to Green Book guidance, and so as a regulatory measure its current efficacy could be considered weak.

Despite the introduction of natural capital concepts within strands of overarching UK policy, largely these currently remain just that – conceptual. In 2020, the Natural Capital Committee, for example, found 'limited evidence of natural capital being considered in policy appraisal' recognising this as a 'failure to implement Green Book guidance... [that] should be urgently addressed' (2020, p.1). The committee noted a need for relevant natural capital tools, as well as independent, expert advice on natural capital valuation, and recommended that impacts on natural capital should be made compulsory criteria for policy impact assessments. An article from the Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management (CIEEM) in 2019 commenting on the inclusion of natural capital approaches in the Green Book for policy appraisal stressed the need for their embedding within decision making 'at every level for public spending and land management' (2019, p.6) and called for the introduction of a requirement for natural capital and ecosystem services impact assessment within local planning authority impact assessments and environmental assessments, for collaborative partnerships to build and monitor natural capital assessments and valuations and for local partnerships to establish management plans for the enhancement and protection of natural capital.

Despite the conceptual nature of most discussions of natural capital concepts in UK policy, therefore, there are nevertheless some promising signs that the ground is being prepared for a more practical application and that there is a will in some sectors to challenge and innovate traditional forms of economic thinking. The implementation of a more obligatory approach within high level policies and instruments such as the Green Book might provide clearer signals to policymakers that operationalisation is necessary, but it remains to be seen whether this will occur or whether the tools and knowledge needed for this to happen are yet available. Conceptual discussion of the four capitals from the ONS and within other sectors is of interest but the development of functional frameworks for instrumentalising this approach may be years away.

It is clear, then, that examples of UK policies which operationalise, actively regulate or impart obligations to implement natural capital approaches are few and far between. For Scotland this means that while there may be signals from the UK that natural capital should be considered in policy making, there needs to be a push from within to actualise this.

3.32 Natural Capital in High Level and Secondary Policy Across Selected Scottish Policy Sectors

Within Scotland there appears to be a concerted push to incorporate natural capital principles in policy as evidenced in the following section. Scotland is keen to show itself as a leader in this regard, and to 'secure first-mover advantage' (Scottish Government, 2022) both in economic terms and in order to create new natural capital markets. The establishment of the 'Interim Principles for responsible investment in natural capital' (Scottish Government, 2022 [2]) shows both a will to incorporate natural capital thinking across all policy sectors and a recognition that guidelines need to be in place right away, even while theoretical and policy thinking in this area is currently catching up. The establishment of the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital in 2013 indicates that thinking in this area has been simmering for some time and the existence of its four interest groups which draw on stakeholder experience is a positive sign of government aims to ensure development of policies which operationalise natural capital approaches in ways which are inclusive and relevant for all and thus actively functional.

In addition to these specific natural capital policies and initiatives, Scotland's commitment to enacting natural capital approaches within wider policy is clear and, like the UK, it is within economic policy that the most interesting developments are taking place, indicating a recognition of the importance of natural capital to Scotland's economy. Despite a lack of inclusion of natural capital ideas within the 'Economic Action Plan 2019-20' (Scottish Government, 2019 [1]), the positioning of natural capital indicators as markers of economic success within the National Performance Framework indicators shows a clear expectation by the Scottish Government for the sustained technical collection of natural capital data. This may well provide the kind of impetus for operationalising natural capital on the ground that is so far missing in high level UK policy.

Similarly to the UK, there is also a push within economic policy to include different types and conceptions of wealth beyond natural capital approaches. The paper 'Towards a robust, resilient wellbeing economy for Scotland' (Scottish Government, 2020 [4]) highlights Scottish government eagerness to incorporate the four capitals '(natural, social, economic, human)' to encompass a more holistic, wellbeing approach to the Scottish Economy in line with the National Performance Framework. Scotland's natural capital is described as 'an area of significant comparative advantage'

(2020, p.48) and thus as holding a key, underpinning role in Scotland's economic recovery from the shocks of Brexit and the pandemic. It reiterates that as such nature-based investments should be developed by the government to 'protect and enhance' natural capital (2020, p.48) and that natural capital approaches should be embedded across policy. Echoes of these ideas are found in 'Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation' (Scottish Government, 2022 [8]), Programme for Scotland 2020-21 (Scottish Government, 2020 [2]) and Programme for Government 2022-23 (Scottish Government, 2022) however, like the UK, Scotland's interest in the four capitals and alternative measures of wealth remains theoretical and it remains to be seen to what level thinking in this regard will reach.

Beyond these advances some trickle-down of natural capital ideas can be seen across the policy sectors but in their current form, this is almost entirely conceptual. There is little to operationalise or regulate natural capital approaches in climate change policy or conservation and biodiversity policy, for example, aside from the implementation of the Natural Capital Asset Index (2022) by NatureScot which usefully sits alongside the UK's National Capital Accounts to track and research Scotland's natural capital assets. Within Scottish planning and land management policy we see a similar lack of operationalising of natural capital ideas although through grey literature such as 'Land use – getting the best from our land: strategy 2021 to 2026' (Scottish Government, 2021) and 'Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement' (Scottish Government, 2017 [1]) we see conceptual echoes of the four capitals theory and ideas of managing land for cultural and social benefits to achieve economic gains which are starting to influence high level Scottish economic policy thinking.

In terms of Scottish agricultural policy, it is clear that behind the scenes the ground is being prepared for change and this is to be expected as we enter a new post CAP era. As yet public facing communications remain unclear on the extent to which natural capital approaches will be implemented as part of this and in what forms, but we can hope that future conditionality for funding in agriculture will include requirements for natural capital accounting, for example, and indeed the inclusion of requirements to establish baseline levels of environmental performance and efficiency within the current National Test Programme hints at a future requirement for natural capital data collection on farms. The NatureScot 'Farming with Nature' pilot projects provide more robust evidence that natural capital assessment is likely to form the basis for some conditionality payments and that tools to aid in the collection and recording of data in this regard could soon be available. Furthermore, the development and trialling of Regional Land Use Partnerships indicates that there are plans to embed natural capital approaches at levels beyond individual farms within collaborative networks at landscape scale that are inclusive of stakeholders at all levels of governance and participation.

Although it appears that in Scotland, current examples of policy capable of operationalising or regulating natural capital approaches are lacking, developments in agricultural policy seem to suggest that efforts to rapidly operationalise, incentivise and perhaps regulate them are underway and we may see more clarity on what this means in practice when the new Scottish Agricultural Bill is presented in 2023 (McKay, 2022). As-yet the National Performance Framework provides the only tangibly practical impetus for actioning natural capital approaches on the ground and how this will be done remains unclear, but it may be that agricultural policy reform is intended to fill this gap. At a conceptual level, Scotland appears firm in its desire to see natural capital approaches actualised and its focus on the four capitals and alternative wellbeing measures of wealth is promising, echoing UK ONS ambitions to explore inclusive wealth thinking. Within each of the policy sectors analysed there remain opportunities for the facilitation of regulatory and operationalising initiatives through secondary policies such as environmental or planning impact assessments or via the SRDP.

3.33 Natural Capital in Forest Policy

Given the extent to which natural capital concepts and approaches are beginning to conceptually inform overarching and cross-sectoral UK and Scottish policy, we will now focus our attention on natural capital within UK, and then Scottish, forest and woodland policy, and to what extent and in what ways natural capital ideas are conceptualised, operationalised or regulated in forest policy.

- UK Forest Policy

Given the importance of the UKFS (2017) to forestry across the devolved nations it is disappointing to find that it has not yet been updated to include proper discussion of natural capital approaches at conceptual, operational or regulatory levels. It is interesting to note, however, that Defra's 'Government Forestry Policy Statement' (2013) includes mention of natural capital, most notably in declaring government intention to work with the NCC and ONS on developing the UK's Natural Capital Accounts for UK forestry, to develop a 'woodland ecosystem market roadmap' (p.25) and to work to develop ecosystem markets. The statement commits to valuing the 'social and environmental benefits of woodlands and to developing new market opportunities to realise these' (p.4).

More promisingly, however, the Science and Innovation Strategy for Forestry in Great Britain (Welsh Government, Defra, Scottish Forestry, and Forestry Commission, 2020) explicitly and implicitly highlights a prioritisation of collective research across forestry policy, practice and academia into natural capital concepts and more importantly, methods of operationalising them, including research around the development of technical and finance support mechanisms and which engages private sector involvement and investment. Since its creators consider its remit to include feeding into the evidence on which the UKFS is based and into its supporting guidance mechanisms, it could be that changes to the UKFS which reflect natural capital approaches and feed into the devolved forestry policies and their secondary policies are on their way as a result.

At present, however, at the secondary policy level, English woodland policies which could operationalise natural capital approaches do not currently do so, although many of the instruments described would seem to have the capacity to provide avenues for instrumentalising natural capital in the future.

Nevertheless, there are other signs to imply that the UK might be heading for a series of policy advances which operationalise and lead to the regulation of natural capital valuation in the UK's woodlands and forests. The UK Expert Committee on Forest Science (HM Government, 2022 [3]) provides independent advice and assurance to the UK Forestry Commissioners and Forestry Governance Group on the quality of science and evidence supporting forest policy across the UK, including the devolved nations, produced by the Forestry Commission's research agency Forest Research. The presence of leading natural resource, ecological and climate change economist, the PI of KHI-D5-1, Professor Maria Nijnik on this committee indicates a strong likelihood that work in this regard may already be underway.

What is clear is that forest and woodland policy from the UK government as well as instruments from related bodies that enact policy are not yet far advanced with respect to natural capital concepts. However, they are broadly conceptually embedded with ecosystem services thinking and there are exciting signs that the UK government, alongside the governments of the devolved nations, are committed to the research and development of natural capital concepts and their instrumentalization. We can be hopeful that policy which encourages or operationalises natural capital valuations for

forests and woodlands may follow as a result. It remains true that in comparison to other policy sectors, forest policy is currently lagging behind and there is no impetus here with which to catalyse operational change in UK forestry as a whole or in Scotland; however, given the evidence, it seems this may not be true for long. It will be interesting to see to what extent the research initiatives described will influence future iterations of the UKFS and whether a bolder approach which prioritises the operationalising and regulation of natural capital approaches might prompt a revamping of devolved policy material across the UK, including in Scotland.

- Scottish Forest Policy

There is little within Scotland's forestry policies on natural capital approaches, although thinking which considers the economic value of forests beyond the market value of forest products can be seen within instruments, such as 'Scotland's Forestry Strategy: 2019-2029 overview' (Scottish Government, 2019). Although Scottish adherence to the UKFS is highlighted here, as we have seen, this does not itself currently create a huge impetus for actualising natural capital approaches. However, it is heartening to note the key involvement of Scottish Forestry in the authorship of the Science and Innovation Strategy for Forestry in Great Britain (Welsh Government, Defra, Scottish Forestry, and Forestry Commission, 2020) which promises to bring changes in this respect. This indicates a promising commitment to the exploration of natural capital concepts and of ways to operationalise and incentivise them in practice.

Meanwhile, although there is acknowledgement of the focus on natural capital within the National Performance Framework there is nothing to specify how forest strategy will contribute natural capital data to the relevant Indicator. In drawing links within forest policy to the Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital there are further indications that sectoral thinking recognises a need to step forward in this area but so far inclusion of these ideas remains conceptual.

It is clear that the social and human benefits of woodlands are recognised within Scotland, although they are not yet being valued as part of natural capital accounting processes; Scottish Forestry's 'Branching Out' (2022 [1]) programme, for example, offers therapeutic support through woodland activities for adults with mental health issues and is an excellent example of Scotland's progressive thinking in this regard. However, whilst it may be that some of these features of Scottish forestry recognise a wider set of forest benefits for natural, social and human capital alongside the more usually recognised economic benefits, specific conceptual linkages to the 'four capitals' thinking presented in the National Performance Framework or even just to natural capital thinking are currently missing.

Similarly to the UK's forestry sector, then, in comparison to other policy sectors, Scotland's forestry and woodland policy is currently lagging behind in terms of the embedding of natural capital concepts and approaches. This is particularly true in respect of policies which operationalise or regulate natural capital approaches or that provide technical advice on how to do so. There are opportunities here for Scotland to provide data to support the monitoring of natural capital under the National Performance Framework, to encourage investment into forest capital and to actualise the four capitals approach by extending conceptual linkages to already existing ideas on forest benefits for human and social capital. At present, however, Scotland appears to be several steps away from each of these goals. Scotland's focus on research into natural capital concepts in the forestry sector hints at positive

change, however, and we wait with interest to see how this potentially innovative work manifests in Scottish forest policy.

3.34 Public Mechanisms for Supporting Landowners with Natural Capital Approaches

Focusing on the following research question, this section discusses the implications for the operationalising of natural capital approaches on the ground of a variety of public technical and financial support mechanisms in the UK and Scotland.

- What technical or financial support is available in the public sphere for landowners to operationalise natural capital approaches?
- UK Technical and Financial Support Mechanisms

Whilst efforts are being made to incentivise natural capital approaches through financial support measures and offer technical guidance at the UK and English levels, CIEEM's (2019) critique of the UK approach to natural capital implementation suggests that while ELMS may be a positive step forward, clarity on how these incentives will work in practice is required. Willingness to conduct early trials and pilots indicates government interest in actualising the approach but it appears too early to tell exactly how the schemes will be rolled out and to what extent they will be successful in the UK. The ENCA suite offers reasonably comprehensive technical advice but is intended for a different market of stakeholders, and given the great variety of different approaches and options described may cause confusion for landowners on what steps should actually be taken. Meanwhile key government forest and woodland support mechanisms in the finance and technical categories lack any inclusion of natural capital guidance or funding.

Outside of government-initiated mechanisms, support offerings from independent bodies appear more functional; BS 8632 provides a useful technical standard for implementing natural capital approaches which nevertheless remains optional rather than regulatory, while the Natural Capital Protocol offers a useful step by step framework for implementation alongside the provision of urgently needed sectoral guides. Its sister protocols on human and natural capital may eventually provide a connecting point between conceptual four capitals thinking in UK and Scottish policy and technical guidance for operationalising alternative measures of wealth beyond natural capital in practice but such steps are seem more achievable in the long- rather than short-term.

While UKWAS and the FSC are currently lacking in any form of technical support offering for certifying natural capital approaches, they could in theory be adapted to include a natural capital assessment or natural capital accounting requirement as a condition of certification and thus offer a potential avenue for technical support and even regulation. Indeed 'The Natural Capital Protocol: Forest Products Sector Guide' (Natural Capital Coalition, 2018) describes how a natural capital perspective allows environmental issues to be addressed as interrelated issues rather than isolated ones and calls for greater connection between natural capital assessments and forest certification programmes like UKWAS and the FSC. In this way they foresee efforts around the collection of data, and resources and investment created and utilised during the fulfilment of both could be combined and capitalised upon (p.15).

It is apparent, then, that in the UK (and England) there is a lack of practical support in most categories for landowners to operationalise natural capital approaches on the ground. Nevertheless there are initiatives that show promise in offering both technical and financial support in this area. What is needed is focused attention and learning from focused practical trials of these approaches to take them from being good ideas to being functional incentivising and technical instruments that act to operationalise and make it possible to regulate natural capital approaches in practice.

- Scottish Technical and Financial Support Mechanisms

At a devolved level there may be more opportunities for Scottish Government and for those who enact government policy to operationalise natural capital approaches, although so far few of these opportunities have been actualised.

None of the funding schemes under the ‘Scottish Rural Development Programme (SRDP)’ (Scottish Government, 2022 [9]), for example, specify the inclusion of natural capital approaches as criteria for application success – however natural capital projects which focuses on ecosystem service management, involve innovative approaches to enhancing environmental performance, promote knowledge sharing in agriculture or forestry or include elements which promote biodiversity enhancement or emissions reductions might be applicable here. There are elements within the SRDP which chime with the UK government’s new Environmental Land Management Scheme and it will be interesting to see whether once it is up and running natural capital approaches will be explicitly included in the criteria. Beyond the SRDP there are no financial support mechanisms for natural capital approaches in agriculture and hence, with some careful changes, there are opportunities here for Scottish Government to make inroads into operationalising natural capital approaches.

In terms of public forestry financing mechanisms, there is currently nothing provided by the Scottish Government which explicitly facilitates the operationalising of natural capital approaches but there appear to be a few avenues through which incentives could be offered if the government saw fit. It may be that the ‘Forestry Grant Scheme’ (2022) and Forestry Co-operation grant (2017), for example, could be adapted to include criteria for projects that use natural capital approaches. Likewise, the Scottish Forestry ‘Community Fund’ (2022 [2]) offers nothing explicit on natural capital but it may be an avenue for groups wishing to kick start a deliberative process around natural capital valuation, for example, while under the Small Woodland Loan Scheme from Scottish Forestry (2022 [4]) applicants must prove that planting will enhance economic, environmental and social benefits. Again, whilst natural capital projects are not explicitly discussed there may be opportunities for successful financial support here also.

Within the area of non-government funding options for woodland and forest projects, there are also opportunities for natural capital projects to receive financial support. Future Woodlands Scotland’s Research and Innovation grant scheme (2022, 3) demonstrates a willingness to fund projects which show ‘the contribution of native woodlands to the mitigation of and adaptation to climate change;... [or] the contribution which native woodlands can make to the environmental improvement, conservation of the natural heritage or the economic and social vitality of communities...’ (2022, 2). Although not explicitly mentioned, as an innovative approach, a natural capital assessment and management plan could fall within this remit. Furthermore, locally-based funders such as the Borders Forest Trust ‘Woodland Creation Advisory Service’ (2022) may in future be able to provide opportunities for financial support for natural capital projects. Finally, although not explicitly

discussed, National Lottery and Scottish Environment Protection Agency (2022) funding may also be applicable to natural capital projects within either the forest or agriculture sectors.

In terms of technical support mechanisms, there is a wider range of resources available to landowners that more explicitly address the actioning of natural capital approaches. Between them, the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital and the Farm Advisory Service (2022, 1, Scottish Government, 2022 [1]), run under the SRDP, alongside technical offerings from NatureScot, Scottish Land & Estates and the Scottish Community Alliance's 'Community Learning Exchange' (2022) offer excellent coverage of natural capital issues and learning options, tools, alongside opportunities for knowledge exchange and networking in this area. In particular the government's Farm Advisory Service is due to expand and could be an excellent vehicle for government advice and funding for natural capital projects for farmers and crofters.

Within the forestry sector there is little, as-yet, to support natural capital approaches through knowledge- and tool-based means for forestry from the Scottish Government. The 'Integrating Trees Network' (2022) for example as yet offers nothing on natural capital but could perhaps usefully include such information in the future. Meanwhile in the area of forest certification, similarly to the UK's UKWAS and FSC, the UK Woodland Carbon Code (2022) may provide opportunities for the incorporation of requirements for natural capital approaches under its schemes. Unlike the UK schemes, however, inroads have already been made in this regard with the augmentation of 'additionality tests' (Scottish Forestry, 2022 [3]) to align with the Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital. This illustrates one of the few examples of explicit attempts to operationalise natural capital approaches within the Scottish forestry sector.

Outside of government resourced support, there is also very little in the way of technical support for forestry in the public sphere, although organisations capable of offering such support given the correct training and resources themselves do exist. In particular, as an organisation which already usefully provides training on woodland management the Community Woodlands Association would seem to be an organisation that could deliver useful natural capital training in the future.

In Scotland, then, whilst there is currently a dearth of explicit financial support for landowners or woodland / forest managers to operationalise natural capital approaches, there may be a number of opportunities for the government to implement these if the will is there. The Farm Advisory Service is perhaps the most promising avenue so far for the provision of technical support and for signposting users to avenues of financial support. It is clear however that the support landscape must be enhanced to keep up with the rate of change which is signalled by the conceptual advances within Scottish policy and indeed UK policy around natural capital and the four capitals approach. Additionally, in order to realise their ambitions to operationalise natural capital approaches it may be important in the coming years for Scotland to increase its engagement in practical trials to increase learning and experience in this area.

3.35 Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches

The following section discusses the evidence gathered on the following research question, with regards to the UK and then Scotland: What level of involvement does the private sector have in natural capital approaches and how is this facilitated?

- Private Sector Involvement in the UK

Although there do not appear to be many examples of private mechanisms for supporting landowners with the application of natural capital approaches in the UK, a few do exist, indicating that businesses are starting to recognise the importance of natural capital to their financial bottom lines and the business risks intrinsic to its deterioration. Some are taking steps to protect and enhance what they see as agricultural assets and trials in these areas provide excellent examples for future leveraging of private investment. For example, Nestle's trial of PbR incentives for dairy farmers mirrors to some extent the UK government's ELMS. Nestle plans to roll out a similar natural capital partnership approach across other sectors at a regional scale and hopes eventually to involve local governments and 'regional networks of businesses' (p.11). A second pilot is being prepared for Cumbria under the LENS scheme (see below).

Three other notable examples of private trading systems set up independently of government currently exist in the UK. An interesting example is EnTrade (2022), Wessex Water's innovative online platform for reverse auctioning nature-based solutions for environmental services. Nothing specific on natural capital is mentioned but similar trading models have shown that approaches such as this can be applied successfully to natural capital projects. The successful Landscape Enterprise Network (LENS) trading platform for blended-finance nature-based solutions (LENS, 2022) also does not currently highlight natural capital projects for trade, but it seems likely to be able to incorporate such schemes. A similar style of trading model, Natural Infrastructure Schemes (NIS) (Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017) currently exist only in theory having not yet been trialled. Trading platforms such as these may also be able to provide tangible avenues for funding from private investors for landowners who protect and enhance natural capital and ecosystem services.

Alongside efforts from the private sector to involve itself in the protection of natural capital assets in order to protect its business interests, the involvement of private business in natural capital activities in the UK also occurs due to efforts by government or local authorities themselves to attract private investment. The Forestry Commission, for example, have created a prospectus of projects focused around nature for investment which do not currently highlight natural capital but which demonstrate the potential of public sector trading platforms. Under ELMS trials blended finance options are being tested, funded by the Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund, which has been set up to bolster natural capital projects to reach a stage of preparation necessary for attracting private investment.

Additionally, the Council for Sustainable Business, an independent panel of business leaders set up to advise Defra on involving the private sector in environmental protection issues is another new body which has not yet clarified the extent to which it will attempt to advance natural capital issues. However, a tickbox of actions that businesses are asked to agree to in an early campaign to garner private sector support includes commitments to identify and set targets to reduce harmful impacts and dependencies on nature and biodiversity and this may be a positive nod towards the language of impacts and dependencies on ecosystem services that is found in other natural capital-related policy instruments and academic research. Furthermore several smaller examples of interesting blended-finance options also exist which demonstrate the capabilities of local authorities in attracting private finance into natural capital or environmental enhancement projects.

Another area in which the private sector is involved in supporting natural capital approaches in the UK is in the area of paid service provision. UK estate agents and property consultants Strutt and Parker (2022), for example, offer a natural capital accounts service to clients to show how business and

nature impact upon each other. They work to BSI standards to identify costs and benefits of future land management plans. The service is paid for by landowners. Opportunities for paid service provision of this kind are only likely to increase if the operationalising and regulating of natural capital approaches advances in the UK.

Finally, several interesting non-government initiatives exist for generating and sharing knowledge and learning on how to incentivise businesses to protect natural capital assets. The Natural Capital Impact Group (NCIG) for example seeks to generate best-practice knowledge on private investment for natural capital from case studies and looks to be an excellent source of research on frameworks for private sector investment in natural capital and other relevant business solutions. Furthermore 'The Natural Capital Protocol: Forest Products Sector Guide' (Natural Capital Coalition, 2018) calls for joined up corporate thinking which links and integrates information around financial, natural and social capitals into every level of business decision making and reporting in the forest products sector and explores suggestions on how to do this on a practical level. Other guides exist alongside this to promote similar methods of engagement within other business sectors.

- Private Sector Involvement in Scotland

In recent years, there has been a concerted push to include goals for private investment in Scottish policy in recognition of the need for additional sources of funding to address the scale of challenge facing its natural capital assets and ecosystem services, and its continued biodiversity loss; the 25 Year Environment Plan (Scottish Government, 2018), for example, calls for increased private investment into natural capital as do the 'Interim Principles for responsible investment in natural capital' (Scottish Government, 2022 [2]), 'Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation' (Scottish Government, 2022 [8]), Scotland's Programme for Government 2022-23 (Scottish Government, 2022) and 'Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032: securing recovery on a path to net zero' (Scottish Government, 2020 [5]).

The SEPA- and Scottish Wildlife Trust-led Route Map to £1 Billion (SEPA and Scottish Wildlife Trust, 2020) is an exciting collaborative endeavour undertaken in partnership with a large stakeholder group to create an operational plan for securing such investment through a variety of finance and investment initiatives, including, for example, the Natural Capital Pioneer Fund, which matches investors with businesses seeking loans for biodiversity or natural capital enhancing projects. A number of other initiatives are also proposed which employ innovative investment options including, for example, exploration of the use of trading platforms via a partnership with LENSs (see above), and nature-based carbon credit schemes via standards-based schemes the UK Woodland Carbon Code (2022) and the IUCN UK Peatland Code (2022), both of which are currently hosted in Scotland and encourage important private investment into natural capital. Moreover, Riverwood, an active trial of a blended finance model for investment in landscape-scale biodiversity projects, here focused on the development and restoration of riparian woodland and of Scotland's river-landscape, is currently underway.

Alongside these plans and practical projects, the government has taken further steps to actualise their ambitions to attract private investment by launching the Green Investment Portfolio (Scottish Government, 2020 [1]), in 2020. At this stage there are no projects included which explicitly highlight natural capital approaches but given the reiteration of government aspirations for the securing of

private investment in this area it seems hopeful that the portfolio will move in this direction once it is more firmly established.

Finally, in the area of research and development, Scotland is exploring the potential of a new biodiversity credit scheme and related market via a multi-partner approach led by the Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers, a collaborative network focused on the development of markets and investment for natural capital and nature-based solutions which is itself part of the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital. At the same time the Scottish Environment Protection Agency, Scotland's environmental regulator legally empowered by the Scottish Government, has been conducting research via the Natural Environment Research Council funded 'Valuing Nature Programme' from 13th Nov 2017-30th March 2018 with the backing of the Scottish Forum on Natural Capital to explore the state of private investment into land management for the protection of natural capital.

Beyond government efforts, several examples of potential avenues for landowner support are also noted here. Originally, a woodland owner's cooperative, Scottish Woodlands (2022, 1, 2, and 3) is a primarily employee owned, forestry management, investment and acquisition service offering additional options to aid landowners in forest management and access to a group Certification scheme for UKWAS, FSC and PEFC. Various valuation and forestry mapping services are offered if landowners can afford to pay for them. It may be that they or businesses like them might be in a position to, or could be incentivised by the government to, offer natural capital valuations as part of their business plan. Finally, investment management consultants like the Baillie Gifford partnership might also have a part to play in providing private investment for natural capital schemes. Baillie Gifford (2022) offer philanthropic support for charities and not-for-profits and have been instrumental in financing the natural capital work of the Borders Forest Trust, for example.

The strength of Scottish commitment to attracting private investment into natural capital is clear and it is positive to note that beyond the numerous statements made in key policy instruments to this effect, tangible efforts have been made to draw out pathways to achieving this aim. Investment is already occurring and what is most promising are the signals Scotland is sending around its eagerness to take collaborative, inclusive action in this area rather than employing purely top-down approaches.

3.36 Limitations of the Review and Opportunities for Future Natural Capital Research in the Scottish and UK Policy Context

As a systematic approach was not taken, it must be recognised that the search for relevant high level or secondary policy material, technical and finance mechanisms and operational, conceptual or regulatory examples, or for examples of private sector involvement in natural capital approaches, is not exhaustive and that there may be other interesting and useful examples that have not been included. Conclusions drawn are thus intended as a starting point for further, more systematic research for which there is certainly scope.

Due to time limitations a number of interesting areas which relate to, or may impact upon, the embedding and operationalising of natural capital in the Scottish or UK policy contexts have not been included. These therefore provide opportunities for fruitful future research. An analysis which includes the key supranational policies which impact upon Scotland's natural capital policy landscape may be useful, as might a review of the extent and ways in which natural capital are incorporated in policy in Wales and Northern Ireland provide a useful point of comparison. A search of relevant Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) projects and trials might be a relevant addition to enrich the material on

private sector involvement in, or public technical and finance mechanisms for, supporting natural capital approaches. A wider search which includes trials of all natural capital approaches being operationalised in the UK and Scotland and which draws together lessons learnt to generate best-practice policy advice would certainly be instructive. As our specific focus has been on natural capital in forest policy we have looked only at land-based initiatives and research which considers marine natural capital policy has not been included and may produce a usefully aligned analysis. Finally, it has been noted by ENCA (Defra, 2021) that at a local level, natural capital concepts may not be described using natural capital terminology but may be found using the key words of 'green infrastructure', while from other perspectives the terminology of 'nature-based solutions' is often used to describe activities which protect or enhance natural capital. While this report has touched on some activities which focus on these different terminologies a more focused search in these areas may prove an interesting area for future research which reveals the extent of, for example, local authority involvement in natural capital approaches and the forms these take.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]) has highlighted the importance of embedding natural capital approaches in policy decision making in order to operationalise alternative conceptions of wealth which include an understanding of the sustainable management of natural capital as central to economic success and to more holistic measures of wellbeing. The UK and specifically Scotland have signalled their ambitions to incorporate these approaches within the fabric of 'how they do policy' and to position themselves at the head of this tide-change. However, although the last five years have seen a flurry of activity from both governments, it seems on the face of it that action in this area remains largely focused around incorporating conceptualisations of natural capital approaches within high level policy (such as the '25 Year Plan' for the UK (HM Government, 2018 [1]) and the 'Interim Principles' for Scotland (2022 [2])). Whilst the incorporation of natural capital concepts within both the Green and Blue Books in the UK (HM Treasury, 2022; Defra 2022; and ONS, 2021, 2) and the take up of natural capital as an indicator of economic success in the National Performance Framework in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2022 [4]) demonstrate a positive willingness from both nations to reconceptualise economic thinking at the highest level of economic policy, so far it is only the National Performance Framework that has provided any form of incentive or obligatory impetus for policymakers to find ways to actualise these ideas and as such, unsurprisingly trickle-down of natural capital approaches into secondary policy has been slow across other sectors. Rapid change in the agriculture sectors of both nations, however, particularly for Scotland, might signal a switch from conceptual to operational focus and it may be that regulatory change will follow suit, as may the development and provision of technical and financial support mechanisms.

In order to speed the process of permeation into secondary policy in the UK, including an obligatory or regulatory aspect to Green Book guidance seems key to influencing a systematic operationalising of natural capital approaches within secondary policy and indeed, across the devolved nations. Since there seems to be no such impetus from the UK upon Scotland at this point it is fortuitous that Scotland, keen to show itself as an early forerunner of natural capital approaches, has taken steps to be a self-starter in this regard. Nevertheless, there are major opportunities for the operationalising of natural capital approaches in both nations across sectors via the revamping of regulatory instruments which assess policy impacts, for example; practical action to reform secondary policy in this regard is urgently needed to actualise these potential openings.

Within forest policy it appears vital to decisively embed natural capital concepts within the UKFS in order to kick-start change across the devolved forest policies of the whole of the UK, including Scotland, which take their lead from this instrument. As part of this a regulatory element which obliges the incorporation of natural capital accounting into information gathering and subsequent decision-making processes, via impact assessments for example, is urgently required. Forests and woodlands are an intrinsically important component of the UK's natural capital and to match ONS ambitions for the introduction of alternative measures of wealth as well as calls for inclusive wealth accounting from the Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]) they must be reframed more definitively here as a significant indicator of the UK's economic success. Our hope is that pioneering research carried out in response to the Science and Innovation Strategy for Forestry in Great Britain (Welsh Government, Defra, Scottish Forestry, and Forestry Commission, 2020) may catalyse change in this area although how quickly these changes may come remains to be seen. For Scotland, the forest sector is capable of forming a significant contribution to the understandings which will spring from the National Performance Framework's natural capital indicator and secondary policy which regulates decision making must be redrawn to articulate an operationalising impetus for forest owners and managers. Altogether the evidence suggests a dynamic reform of forest policy is required.

Since policy which operationalises and regulates natural capital approaches implies ground-level action from landowners and managers in response, public technical and finance mechanisms to support these changes must be in place. Opportunities for including natural capital approaches in current funding for land and forest management exist both in the UK and Scotland but many of these have yet to be actualised and where frameworks for funding already recognise natural capital projects within success criteria (such as is the case with ELMS) greater clarity is needed on how to make this work in practice. Nonetheless lessons learnt from trials of ELMS could usefully influence Scotland's implementation of the SRDP to ensure it is inclusive of natural capital approaches, while in turn, Scotland's NatureScot 'Farming with Nature' pilots promise fruitful understandings of outcomes-based funding for natural capital projects which could equally be shared. Within the category of technical support, early signs suggest that the UK could learn much from Scotland's Farm Advisory Service which may provide a more targeted and easily navigable source of knowledge and learning for land and forest owners and managers on natural capital approaches and how to operationalise them in practice than ENCA currently does. Moreover, a recognition of the contributions and needs of non-government bodies who play a significant role in enacting government policy and themselves provide access to technical and financial support for land and forest owners and managers to implement them on the ground would be of use.

In the area of private sector involvement in natural capital approaches (which falls into the finance and investment category of government decision-making) we can see that a number of trials and early ventures which provide platforms for interesting and innovative mechanisms to operationalise the new forms of economic thinking being conceptualised by both governments are occurring. It is interesting that impetus for these efforts stems from both within and outside of government which indicates that some level of harmonious understanding is beginning to form between policymakers and business leaders. From both governments, and particularly for Scotland, thinking seems to reflect the idea that private investment into natural capital may pave the way for its protection and enhancement and there appears to be a discernible move towards approaching natural capital projects in partnership with business using collaborative and inclusive approaches rather than retaining sovereign control. Altogether the picture with regards to private investment and involvement in natural capital approaches in both the UK and Scotland appears to be dynamic and fast-moving and it will be interesting to see how it develops and influences the operationalising and regulating of natural capital approaches and the protection of natural capital assets over time.

It appears that the success of natural capital approaches rests on a recognition of the need for 'collective action' as emphasised in the Dasgupta Review (2021 [1]). A cooperative approach which allows shared learning between the two governments is recommended in order to synthesise and learn from the many strands of innovative action and re-conceptualisation taking place across policy, research, business and ground-level land and forest management at this time. To facilitate this, explicit theoretical links and correspondent pathways for practical action must be drawn between high level policy conceptualisations of natural capital, secondary policy instruments which create impetus for operationalising them, and the various forms of public and private financing and technical support mechanisms which make them possible to achieve on the ground. In this regard initiatives like the Route Map for £1 Billion provide an excellent example of how such collaboration can be facilitated to outline avenues for activity and innovation, indicating that by employing an inclusive, deliberative mindset there may be possibilities for creating a coherence that aligns through policy, at different levels and across sectors, public support mechanisms and private sector engagement and investment mechanisms and initiatives, to promote successful, operational and well-regulated forms of natural capital action on the ground.

Acknowledgement

This project is supported by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division of the Scottish Government through its Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027), in particular project JHI-D5-1 in the Natural Capital Topic.

Bibliography

AECOM and Cumulus Consultants (March 2018) '**Trial of the Natural Capital Protocol for land-based businesses: Overview report for Crown Estate Scotland on behalf of a coalition of organisations**', [Trial of Natural Capital Protocol for land-based businesses - Overview Report \(naturalcapitalscotland.com\)](https://www.naturalcapitalscotland.com) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

Andrews Tipper, W., and Francis, A. (Green Alliance) (2017) '**Natural Infrastructure Schemes in practice: How to create new markets for ecosystem services from land**', [Natural infrastructure schemes in practice.pdf \(green-alliance.org.uk\)](https://www.green-alliance.org.uk) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Baillie Gifford '**Our Story**', [Our Story | Global | Long-term Active Asset & Investment Trust Manager | Baillie Gifford | Baillie Gifford](https://www.bailliegifford.com) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Betts, R. A., and Brown, K. (2021) 'Introduction'. In The Third UK Climate Change Risk Assessment Technical Report [Betts, R. A., Haward, A. B., and Pearson, K. V. (eds)]. Prepared for the Climate Change Committee, London. [Technical-Report-The-Third-Climate-Change-Risk-Assessment.pdf \(ukclimaterisk.org\)](https://www.ukclimaterisk.org) [Online: accessed 11/10/2022].

Borders Forest Trust '**Woodland Creation Advisory Services**', [Borders Forest Trust](https://www.bordersforesttrust.com) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

British Standards Institution (2021) '**BS 8632:2021 Natural capital accounting for organisations. Specification**', [BS 8632:2021 | 30 Jun 2021 | BSI Knowledge \(bsigroup.com\)](https://www.bsigroup.com) [Online: accessed 20/09/2022].

Capitals Coalition (2022) '**Modelling better business: nestle trials natural capital premium with UK dairy farmers**', [Modelling Better Business: Nestlé Trials Natural Capital Premium with UK Dairy Farmers - Capitals Coalition](#) [Online: accessed 03/10/2022]

Capitals Coalition (2021) '**Natural Capital Protocol**', [Natural Capital Protocol – Capitals Coalition](#) (14/01/2021) [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management (CIEEM) (2019) '**Natural Capital and Biodiversity: a briefing note for policy-makers**'

CivTech (2022) '**Innovate for Nature**', [Innovate for Nature — CivTech](#) [Online: accessed 17/11/2022].

Committee on Climate Change (CCC) (2020) '**Land use: policies for a net zero UK**', [Land-use-Policies-for-a-Net-Zero-UK.pdf](#) [Online: accessed 05/10/2022]

Community Woodlands Association (2022) '**Welcome to the community woodland's association**', [Community Woodlands Association \(communitywoods.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022]

Cornwall AONB (2022) '**Protected Landscape Investment Bank**', [Protected Landscape Investment Bank — The Cornwall Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty \(cornwall-aonb.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Council for Sustainable Business (2022) '**The decade of difference: joint action for a carbon negative / nature positive future**', [Home Page | Council for Sustainable Business](#) [Online: accessed 14/11/2022].

Dasgupta, P. (2021) '**The Economics of biodiversity: the Dasgupta review**'. (London: HM Treasury) [1]

Dasgupta, P. (2021) '**The Economics of biodiversity: the Dasgupta review. Headline messages**'. (London: HM Treasury) [2].

Defra (2020) '**Accounting for the Effects of Climate Change: Supplementary Green Book Guidance**', [Accounting for the Effects Of Climate Change - Supplementary Green Book ...pdf \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#). [Online: accessed 15/09/2022]

DEFRA (2007) '**An introductory guide to valuing ecosystem services**', [an introductory guide to valuing ecosystem services \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#). [Online: accessed 16/09/2022]

Defra (2011) '**Biodiversity 2020: a strategy for England's wildlife and ecosystem services**', [pb13583-biodiversity-strategy-2020-111111.pdf \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022]

DEFRA (2010) '**Delivering a healthy natural environment**', [Defra healthy-nat-envIRON.pdf \(ecosystemsknowledge.net\)](#) [Online: accessed 16/09/2022]

Defra (2021) '**ENCA Asset Databook Aug 2021 update**', [ENCA Asset Databook Aug 2021 update.xlsx \(live.com\)](#) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [1]

Defra (2021) '**ENCA Case Studies August 2021 update**', [ENCA Case Studies August 2021 update rev.xlsx \(live.com\)](#) [Online: accessed 09/11/2022] [2]

Defra (2021) '**ENCA Services Databook October 2021 update**', [ENCA Services Databook October 2021 update.xlsm \(live.com\)](#) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [3]

Defra (2021) 'Enabling a Natural Capital Approach Guidance'. [Enabling a Natural Capital Approach \(ENCA\): Guidance - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 12/09/2022] [4]

Defra: (2021) **England Trees Action Plan 2021 to 2024**, [England Trees Action Plan 2021 to 2024 - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#). 18/05/2021 [Online: accessed 13/09/2022] [5]

Defra (2013): **Government Forestry Policy Statement**. [Government forestry policy statement - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) [Online, accessed 12/09/2022]

Defra: (2022) '**Keepers of time: ancient and native woodland trees policy in England. Government's statement on England's ancient and native woodland and ancient and veteran trees**'. [Keepers of time: ancient and native woodland and trees policy in England - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) 27/05/2022 [Online: accessed 13/09/2022] [1]

Defra (2021) '**Local Nature Recovery Strategies**' [Local Nature Recovery Strategies: how to prepare and what to include - Defra - Citizen Space](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [6]

Defra (2022) '**Natural Capital and Ecosystem Assessment Programme**', [Online: accessed 16/09/2022] [2]

Defra (2021) '**Test and Trials Evidence Report: Schemes for environmental land management**', Version 1.0 [Environmental land management: tests and trials - December 2021 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [7]

Defra (2022) '**Trees and Woodland Science Advisory Group**', [Trees and Woodlands Scientific Advisory Group - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#). (Meeting minutes 22 April 2021 – 10th May 2022) [Online: accessed 13/09/2022] [3]

EnTrade '**About Us**', [About us \(entrade.co.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Environment Agency (2022) '**Form: How to apply for a natural environment readiness fund grant**', [\[Withdrawn\] How to apply for a natural environment investment readiness fund grant - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 14/11/2022].

ESCom Scotland [Scotland's Natural Treasures – an illustrated ecosystem services map | Oppla](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

European Commission (2022) '**The Common Agricultural Policy: an overview**', [The Common Agricultural Policy: an overview \(europa.eu\)](#) [Online: accessed 14/10/2022].

Farm Advisory Service '**About Us**' [Home - Farm Advisory Service | Helping farmers in Scotland | Farm Advisory Service \(fas.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022] [1]

Farm Advisory Service (2022) '**Natural Capital: a case study about the reasons for measuring the baseline of natural capital in a landscape, and the practicalities of doing it**', [Natural Capital: a case study about the reasons for measuring the baseline of natural capital in a landscape, and the practicalities of doing it | Information helping farmers in Scotland | Farm Advisory Service \(fas.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [5]

Farm Advisory Service (20th May 2021) '**Study puts a value on natural capital of new woodlands**', [Off-Cuts: Study puts a value on natural capital of new woodlands \(FWN36 Spring 2021\) | Helping farmers in Scotland | Farm Advisory Service \(fas.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [4]

Farm Advisory Service (12th August 2022) '**What is Natural Capital?**', [What is Natural Capital? | Information helping farmers in Scotland | Farm Advisory Service \(fas.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [3]

Farm Advisory Service (2020) '**Woodland creation, management & conservation**', [Woodland creation, management & conservation support | Helping farmers in Scotland | Farm Advisory Service \(fas.scot\)](#) [2]

Forestry and Land Scotland (2021) '**Acquisition Strategy**', [Acquisition Strategy - Forestry and Land Scotland](#) [Online: accessed 23/09/2022]

Forestry Commission: (2020) '**Managing England's woodlands in a climate emergency**'. [Managing England's woodlands in a climate emergency - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 13/09/2022]

Forestry Commission (2022) '**New staffing support for Local Authorities creating woodland to tackle climate change**', [New staffing support for Local Authorities creating woodland to tackle climate change - Forestry Commission \(blog.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 09/1/2022]

Forestry Commission (2017) '**The UK Forestry Standard. The government's approach to sustainable forestry**'. [The UK Forestry Standard \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 13/09/2022].

FSC: (2020) '**Forest Stewardship Council Global Strategy 2021-2026: Demonstrating the value and benefits of forest stewardship**'. ([FSC Global Strategy 2021-2026](#)) (2020) [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

FSC: (2022) '**FSC Standards**', [FSC Standards | Forest Stewardship Council](#). [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

Future Woodlands Scotland (2022) '**Funding opportunities**', [Future Woodlands Fund - Future Woodlands Scotland](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [1]

Future Woodlands Scotland (2022) '**Research and innovation grants**', [RI Grant Application Guidance 2021 \(futurewoodlands.org.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [2]

Future Woodlands Scotland (2022) '**research and innovation grants – how to apply**', [How to Apply - Future Woodlands Scotland](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [3]

Future Woodlands Scotland (2022) '**Who we are**', [Who we are - Future Woodlands Scotland](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [4]

GGKP (2020) '**Practical policy use cases for natural capital information: a review of evidence for the policy relevance and impact of natural capital information**'. Geneva: Green Growth Knowledge Partnership.

HM Government (2018) '**A Green Future: Our 25 year plan to improve the environment**', [25-year-environment-plan.pdf \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [1]

HM Government (2020) '**Agriculture Act 2020**', [Agriculture Act 2020 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [1]

HM Government (2008) '**Climate Change Act 2008**' [Climate Change Act 2008 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022]

HM Government (2021) '**Collection: Importing and exporting wood and timber products**', [Importing and exporting wood and timber products - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [1]

HM Government (2022) '**Council for Sustainable Business**', [Council for Sustainable Business - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/council-for-sustainable-business) [Online: accessed 09/11/2022] [1]

HM Government (2020) '**Countryside Stewardship**', [Countryside Stewardship – GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/countryside-stewardship) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [2]

HM Government (2018) '**Create a woodland management plan**', [Create a woodland management plan - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/countryside-stewardship) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022].

HM Government (2021) '**Environment Act 2021**', [Environment Act 2021 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/17) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [2]

HM Government (2017) '**Environmental Impact Assessment**', [Environmental Impact Assessment - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/environmental-impact-assessment) [Online: accessed 05/10/2022] [1]

HM Government (2021) '**Environmental Land Management Schemes: overview**', [Environmental Land Management schemes: overview - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/environmental-land-management-schemes) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [3]

HM Government (2021) '**Environmental Impact Assessments for woodland**', [Environmental Impact Assessments for woodland - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/environmental-impact-assessments-for-woodland) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [4]

HM Government (2022) '**Expert Committee on Forest Science**', [Expert Committee on Forest Science - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/expert-committee-on-forest-science) [Online: accessed 25/11/2022] [3]

HM Government (2021) '**Guidance: Tree felling: overview**', [Tree felling: overview - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/tree-felling) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [5]

HM Government (2021) '**Guidance: Plant Health legislation for forestry**', [Plant Health legislation for forestry - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/plant-health-legislation-for-forestry) [Online: accessed 08/11/2022] [6]

HM Government (2017) '**Industrial Strategy: building a Britain fit for the future**', [Industrial Strategy: building a Britain fit for the future \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](https://publishing.service.gov.uk/government/organisations/industrial-strategy) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [2]

HM Government (2020) '**Landmark agriculture bill becomes law**', [Landmark Agriculture Bill becomes law - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/landmark-agriculture-bill) [4]

HM Government (2021) '**National Planning Policy Framework**', [National Planning Policy Framework - Guidance - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/national-planning-policy-framework) [Online: accessed 22/09/2022] [7]

HM Government (2021) '**Net Zero strategy: build back greener**', [net-zero-strategy-beis.pdf \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](https://publishing.service.gov.uk/government/organisations/net-zero-strategy) [Online: accessed 21/09/2021] [8]

HM Government (2021) '**Press release: Innovative nature projects awarded funding to drive private investment**', [Innovative nature projects awarded funding to drive private investment - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/press-releases) [Online: accessed 09/11/2022] [9]

HM Government (2022) '**Rural development programme for England**', [Rural Development Programme for England - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/rural-development-programme-for-england) [Online: accessed 05/10/2022] [2]

HM Government (2017) '**The clean growth strategy: leading the way to a low carbon future**', [Clean Growth Strategy \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](https://publishing.service.gov.uk/government/organisations/clean-growth-strategy) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [3]

HM Government (2017) '**The Town and country planning (environmental impact assessment) regulations 2017**', [The Town and Country Planning \(Environmental Impact Assessment\) Regulations 2017 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukreg/2017/1100) [Online: accessed 05/10/2022] [4]

UK Parliament (2020) '**Agriculture Act 2020: Government Bill**', [Agriculture Act 2020 - Parliamentary Bills - UK Parliament](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

HM Treasury '**The Green Book: central government guidance on appraisal and evaluation**', [The Green Book \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#). (2022) [Online: accessed 15/09/2022]

IUCN (2022) '**Our vision**', [IUCN UK Peatland Programme \(iucn-uk-peatlandprogramme.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 17/11/2022].

JNCC [Joint Nature Conservation Committee] and Defra (2012) '**UK Post-2010 Biodiversity Framework**', [UK Post-2010 Biodiversity Framework \(jncc.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022]

Just Transition Commission (2022) '**Just Transition Commission: a national mission for a fairer, greener Scotland: Executive summary**', [Just Transition Commission Executive Summary \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Kenter, Reed, Irvine, O'Brien, Brady, Bryce, Christie, Church, Cooper, Davies, Evely, Everard, Fazey, Hockley, Jobstvogt, Molloy, Orchard-Webb, Ravenscroft, Ryan, Watson, (2014) '**UKNEAFO Work Package 6: Shared, plural and cultural values of ecosystems – Summary**', [D0 WP5 Summary \(unep-wcmc.org\)](#), [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

LENs (Landscape Enterprise Networks) '**What is LENs?**', [Landscape Enterprise Networks – A 3Keel initiative to support resilient landscapes](#). [Online: accessed 04/10/2022]

McKay, D. (2022) '**Post-CAP agricultural policy in Scotland**', *Soil Association Scotland*, [Post-CAP agricultural policy in Scotland \(soilassociation.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 18/11/2022].

Metzger, M., Dick, J., Gardner, A., Bellamy, C., Blackstock, K., Brown, C., Chisholm, R., Cochrane, P., Drewitt, J., Gimona, A., Hester, A., Mathieson, S., Nijnik, M., McVittie, A., Petr, M., Smith, R., and Smith, M. (2019). '**Knowledge sharing, problem solving and professional development in a Scottish Ecosystem Services Community of Practice**'. *Regional Environmental Change*, Volume 19, [Issue 8: 2275–2286 https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01537-0](#)

Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government (2021) '**National Planning Policy Framework**', [National Planning Policy Framework \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 05/10/2022]

Natural Capital Coalition (2018) '**Natural Capital Protocol: Forest Products Sector Guide**', [Forest Products Sector Guide to the Natural Capital Protocol - World Business Council for Sustainable Development \(WBCSD\)](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022]

Natural Capital Committee, (2022) '**Natural Capital Committee**', [Natural Capital Committee \(NCC\) - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#), [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

Natural Capital Committee (2020) '**The Green Book Guidance: embedding natural capital into public policy appraisal – November 2020 update**', [Natural Capital Committee \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#), [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

Natural England and Forestry Commission: '**Ancient woodland, ancient trees and veteran trees: advice for making planning decisions**'. [Ancient woodland, ancient trees and veteran trees: advice for making planning decisions - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](#) 14/01/2022 [Online: accessed 13/09/2022].

NatureScot (2022) '**Farmer-led projects**', [Farmer-led Projects | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 26/11/2022] [5]

NatureScot (2022) **'Farming with nature'**, [Farming with Nature | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 25/11/2022] [3]

NatureScot (2022) **'NatureScot research report 1260 – Facilitating local natural capital investment – literature review'**, [NatureScot Research Report 1260 - Facilitating Local Natural Capital Investment - Literature Review | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 26/11/2022] [6]

NatureScot (2022) **'Piloting an outcomes based approach in Scotland (POBAS) project, Phase 2 report'**, [Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach in Scotland \(POBAS\) project, Phase 2 report | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 26/11/2022] [4]

NatureScot (2019) **'Piloting natural capital accounts on SNH land'** [Testing a Natural Capital approach on SNH land -summary_0.pdf \(nature.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

NatureScot (2021) **'Principles for Natural Capital Accounting on Public Land in Scotland'**, [070_553_principlesfornaturalcapitalaccountingonpublicland_workinggroupagreedversion_91121_1645702213.pdf \(naturalcapitalscotland.com\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

NatureScot (2020) **'The Natural Capital Asset Index 2020 Comparison Document'**, [The Natural Capital Asset Index 2020 - comparison document | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 13/11/2022]

NatureScot (2022) **'What Is natural capital?'** [Natural Capital | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [1]

NatureScot (2022) **'Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers – Grow, Restore, Prosper'**, [Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers – Grow, Restore, Prosper | NatureScot](#) [Online: accessed 17/11/2022] [2]

Office for Environmental Protection (2022) **'What we do'**, [What we do | Office for Environmental Protection \(theoep.org.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 09/11/2022]

ONS (2021) **'Environmental Accounts'**, [Environmental accounts - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 22/09/2022] [1]

ONS (2022) **'Natural Capital Accounts Roadmap: 2022'**, [Natural capital accounts roadmap - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [1]

ONS (2022) **'New beyond GDP measures for the UK: a workplan for measuring inclusive income'** [New Beyond GDP measures for the UK: a workplan for measuring inclusive income - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [2]

ONS (2021) **'UK National Accounts, The Blue Book: 2021'** [UK National Accounts, The Blue Book: 2021 - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 21/09/2022] [2]

ONS (2022) **'UK Natural Capital Accounts'**, [UK natural capital accounts 2021 - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#) (12/11/2021) [Online: accessed 14/09/2022] [3]

Pevensey Coastal Defence Ltd **'Pevensey Bay Sea Defences PPP'**, [PCDL - Pevensey Coastal Defence Ltd \(pevensey-bay.co.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Rivers Trust (2022) **'New opportunities to invest in nature as The Rivers Trust receives £180,000 in funding'**, [New opportunities to invest in nature as The... | The Rivers Trust](#) [Online: accessed 14/11/2022].

Rural Payments Agency (2021) '**Countryside Stewardship 2021: Capital Grants manual (from 9 February 2021)**', [Countryside Stewardship 2021: Capital Grants manual - from 9 February 2021 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [1]

Rural Payments Agency (2021) '**Countryside Stewardship: Mid Tier and Wildlife Offers manual for agreements starting on 1 Jan 2022**', [Countryside Stewardship: Mid Tier and Wildlife Offers manual for agreements starting on 1 January 2022 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [2]

Rural Payments Agency (2021) '**Countryside Stewardship: Higher Tier manual for agreements starting on 1 January 2022**', [Countryside Stewardship: Higher Tier manual for agreements starting on 1 January 2022 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [3]

Rural Payments Agency (2021) '**Countryside Stewardship: Woodland Creation and Maintenance grant manual (from 9 February 2021)**', [Countryside Stewardship: Woodland Creation and Maintenance grant manual \(from 9 February 2021\) \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022] [4]

Rural Payments Agency (2020) '**Woodland Management Plan grant: Countryside Stewardship (from October 2020)**', [Woodland Management Plan grant: Countryside Stewardship \(from October 2020\) \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Scottish Community Alliance '**Community Learning Exchange**', [Community Learning Exchange - Scottish Community Alliance](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), The University of Edinburgh, **Valuing Nature Programme**, Scottish Forum on Natural Capital (13th Nov 2017-30th March 2018) '**Understanding the potential for private sector investment in natural capital – lessons from the Spey catchment: Executive Summary**', [Executive summary \(sepa.org.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022]

Scottish Forestry (2022) '**Branching Out: positive mental health through nature**', [Scottish Forestry - Branching Out](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Forestry (2022) '**Community fund**', [Scottish Forestry - Community Fund](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Forestry (2022) '**Rules strengthened around woodland carbon schemes**', [Scottish Forestry - Rules strengthened around woodland carbon schemes](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [3]

Scottish Forestry (2022) '**Small Woodland Loan Scheme**', [Scottish Forestry - Small Woodland Loan Scheme](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [4]

Scottish Forestry and Scottish Government '**Integrating Trees Network: a new demonstrator network of farms, crofts and estates**', [Integrating Trees on Your Land - Farming for a Better Climate](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022]

Scottish Forum on Natural Capital '**Who we Are**' [Scottish Forum on Natural Capital \(naturalcapitalscotland.com\)](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2022) '**Agri-Environment Climate Scheme**', [Agri-Environment Climate Scheme \(ruralpayments.org\)](#) [Online: access 29/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2014) '**Ambition, opportunity, place: Scotland's third national planning framework**' [Scotland's Third National Planning Framework \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2022) '**A stronger & more resilient Scotland: the Programme for Government 2022-23**', [stronger-more-resilient-scotland-programme-government-202223.pdf](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2009) '**Climate change (Scotland) Act 2009**', [Climate Change \(Scotland\) Act 2009 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](http://legislation.gov.uk) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2019) '**Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019**', [Climate Change \(Emissions Reduction Targets\) \(Scotland\) Act 2019 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](http://legislation.gov.uk) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Government '**Crofting Agricultural Grant Scheme**', [Crofting Agricultural Grant Scheme \(ruralpayments.org\)](http://ruralpayments.org) [Online: access 29/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2019) '**Economic Action Plan 2019-20: Summary of headline actions**', [Summary of headline actions – mygov.scot \(nrscotland.gov.uk\)](http://nrscotland.gov.uk) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2016) '**Evaluation of the Regional Land Use Frameworks**', [Evaluation of the Regional Land Use Framework Pilots \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2022) '**Farm Advisory Service**', [Advisory service \(ruralpayments.org\)](http://ruralpayments.org) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2018) '**Forestry and Land Management (Scotland) Act 2018**', [Forestry and Land Management \(Scotland\) Act 2018 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](http://legislation.gov.uk) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2017) '**Forestry Co-operation**', [Forestry Co-operation \(ruralpayments.org\)](http://ruralpayments.org) [Online: accessed 16/11/2022]

Scottish Government '**Forestry Grant Scheme**', [Forestry Grant Scheme \(ruralpayments.org\)](http://ruralpayments.org) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2020) '**Green investment portfolio launched**', [Green Investment Portfolio launched - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2022) '**Interim principles for responsible investment in natural capital**', [Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 23/9/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2022) '**Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Fund**', [Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Fund \(ruralpayments.org\)](http://ruralpayments.org) [3]

Scottish Government (2022) '**Landscape and outdoor access**', [Land use - Landscape and outdoor access - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 18/11/2022] [13]

Scottish Government (2021) '**Land use – getting the best from our land: strategy 2021 to 2026**', [Supporting documents - Land use - getting the best from our land: strategy 2021 to 2026 - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](http://www.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2022) '**National performance Framework: Our purpose, values and national outcomes**', [NPF A4 Booklet.pdf \(nationalperformance.gov.scot\)](http://nationalperformance.gov.scot) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [4]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Natural Capital'**, [Natural Capital | National Performance Framework](#) [Online: accessed 14/10/2022] [5]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Preparing for Sustainable farming (PSF)'**, [Preparing for Sustainable Farming \(PSF\) \(ruralpayments.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [6]

Scottish Government (2020) **'Protecting Scotland, renewing Scotland: the Government's Programme for Scotland 2020-2021'**, [Protecting Scotland, Renewing Scotland: The Government's Programme for Scotland 2020-2021 - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022][2]

Scottish Government (2019) **'Protecting Scotland's Future: the Government's Programme for Scotland 2019-2020'**, [The Government's Programme for Scotland 2019-20 \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 18/11/2022] [3]

Scottish Government (2015) **'Scotland's Biodiversity: a route map to 2020'**, [Scotland's Biodiversity: a Route Map to 2020 \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 14/10/2022].

Scottish Government (2019) **'Scotland's Forestry Strategy: 2019-2029 overview'** [Forestry Strategy 2019-2029.pdf](#) [Online: accessed 23/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Scotland's Forestry Strategy Implementation Plan: 2022-2025'**, [Scotland's Forestry Strategy Implementation Plan 2022-2025 Sept 22.pdf](#) [Online: accessed 23/09/2022] [7]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation'**, [Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [8]

Scottish Government (2021) **'Scotland's Third Land Use Strategy 2021-2026: Getting the best from our land'**, [scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land.pdf \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 18/11/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2017) **'Scottish land rights and responsibilities statement'**, [Scottish land rights and responsibilities statement - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2020) **'Scottish Planning Policy'**, [Scottish Planning Policy - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [3]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Scottish Rural Development Programme (SRDP)'** [Scottish Rural Development Programme \(SRDP\) - Agricultural payments: Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\) - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [9]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Scottish Rural Network'**, [Scottish Rural Network \(ruralpayments.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [10]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Small Farms Grant Scheme'**, [Small Farms Grant Scheme \(ruralpayments.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [11]

Scottish Government (2018) **'Stability and Simplicity: proposals for a rural funding transition period'**, [Stability and Simplicity - proposals for a rural funding transition period \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2022) **'Sustainable Agriculture Capital Grant Scheme'**, [Sustainable Agriculture Capital Grant Scheme | Scottish Rural Network](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022] [12]

Scottish Government (2016) '**Sustainable management of forests: woodland grazing**', [Sustainable Management of Forests – Woodland Grazing \(ruralpayments.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Government (2017) '**The Forestry (Environmental Impact Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations 2017**', [The Forestry \(Environmental Impact Assessment\) \(Scotland\) Regulations 2017 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Government (2022) '**The next step in delivering our vision for Scotland as a leader in sustainable and regenerative farming**', [The Next Step In Delivering Our Vision For Scotland As a Leader In Sustainable And Regenerative Farming. \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 18/11/2022] [14]

Scottish Government (2010) '**The right tree in the right place: planning for forestry and woodlands**', [fcaf129.pdf](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2020) '**Towards a robust, resilient wellbeing economy for Scotland**', [Towards a robust, resilient wellbeing economy for Scotland \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 14/10/2022] [4]

Scottish Government (1997) '**Town and Country Planning (Scotland) Act 1997**', [Town and Country Planning \(Scotland\) Act 1997 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2004) '**Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act 2004**', [Nature Conservation \(Scotland\) Act 2004 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 23/09/2022]

Scottish Government (2020) '**Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032: securing a green recovery on a path to net zero**', [Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018 - 2032: Securing a Green Recovery on a Path to Net Zero \(www.gov.scot\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022] [5]

Scottish Land & Estates (2021) '**New regional land use partnerships**', [New regional land use partnerships | Scottish Land & Estates \(scottishlandandestates.co.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Land & Estates (2021) '**New SLC research to examine effect of natural capital and carbon value on land market**', [New SLC research to examine effect of natural capital and carbon value on land market | Scottish Land & Estates \(scottishlandandestates.co.uk\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

Scottish Land & Estates '**ScotLand Matters: The Scottish Land & Estates Podcast. In conversation with: Bidwell's Andy Turnbull & SLE's Stephen Young on natural capital**' [In conversation with: Bidwells' Andy Turnbull & SLE's Stephen Young on natural capital by ScotLand Matters: The Scottish Land & Estates Podcast \(anchor.fm\)](#) [Online: accessed 29/09/2022]

Scottish Land Commission (2022) '**Land rights and responsibilities protocols: responsible natural capital and carbon management**' [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Land Commission (2019) '**Regional Land Use Partnerships**', [Regional Land Use Partnerships - News - News & Events - Scottish Land Commission](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Scottish Wildlife Trust (2022) '**Riverwoods**', [Riverwoods | Scottish Wildlife Trust](#) [Online: Accessed 17/11/2022].

Scottish Woodlands (2022) '**Forest certification**', [Forest Certification | Scottish Woodlands](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [1]

Scottish Woodlands (2022) '**Investment**', [Investment | Scottish Woodlands](#) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [2]

Scottish Woodlands (2022) '**What We Do**', [Search \(scottishwoodlands.co.uk\)](https://www.scottishwoodlands.co.uk) [Online: accessed 26/09/2022] [3]

SEPA '**Looking for funding?**', [Looking for funding? | Scottish Environment Protection Agency \(SEPA\)](https://www.sepa.gov.uk/looking-for-funding) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

SEPA and Scottish Wildlife Trust (2020) 'Route Map to £1 Billion', [202001_1-Billion-Challenge-Document_FINAL.pdf](https://www.sepa.gov.uk/202001-1-Billion-Challenge-Document-FINAL.pdf) [Online: accessed 17/11/2022].

Sheffield City Council '**Lower Don Valley Flood Defence project and Business Improvement District**', [Lower Don Valley Flood Defence project & Business Improvement District | Sheffield City Council](https://www.sheffield.gov.uk/infrastructure/transport/roads/roadworks/roadworks-projects/roadworks-projects-2022/roadworks-projects-2022-1/roadworks-projects-2022-1-1) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

Soil Association Scotland '**Agroforestry**', [Agroforestry \(soilassociation.org\)](https://www.soilassociation.org) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

South of Scotland Enterprise, Dumfries & Galloway Council, Scottish Borders Council (2022) '**South of Scotland Regional Land Use Pilot: Welcome to the consultation hub**', [11780 - South of Scotland Regional Land Use Partnership Pilot \(arcgis.com\)](https://www.arcgis.com) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Strutt and Parker (2020) '**Strutt & Parker in natural capital account collaboration with eftec**', [Natural capital account collaboration with eftec | Rural Hub | Strutt & Parker \(struttandparker.com\)](https://www.struttandparker.com) [Online: accessed 14/11/2022].

Strutt and Parker '**The pitfalls of 'Carbon tunnel vision' for landowners**', [Why farms need to look wider than their carbon emissions \(struttandparker.com\)](https://www.struttandparker.com) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

The National Lottery '**National Lottery Awards for All Scotland**', [National Lottery Awards for All Scotland | The National Lottery Community Fund \(tnlcommunityfund.org.uk\)](https://www.tnlcommunityfund.org.uk) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

The National Lottery '**Scottish Land Fund**', [Scottish Land Fund | The National Lottery Community Fund \(tnlcommunityfund.org.uk\)](https://www.tnlcommunityfund.org.uk) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

The Rivers Trust '**Building nature based solutions**', [Building Nature Based Solutions | The Rivers Trust](https://www.rivers-trust.org.uk) [Online: accessed 06/10/2022]

UKNEA (2011) '**The UK National Ecosystem Assessment: Synthesis of the Key Findings**'. UNEP-WCMC, Cambridge.

UKNEAFO (2014) '**UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow On: Synthesis of the Key Findings**', [UK NEA \(unep-wcmc.org\)](https://www.unep-wcmc.org), [Online: accessed 14/09/2022]

UK Woodland Assurance Standard (UKWAS), 4th edn. [Home - UKWAS](https://www.ukwas.org.uk) [Online: accessed 13/09/2022]

UK Woodland Carbon Code (2022) '**UK Woodland Carbon Code**', [Home - UK Woodland Carbon Code](https://www.ukwcc.org.uk) [Online: accessed 16/11/2022]

University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership Natural Capital Impact Group (2018) '**Modelling Better Business: Nestle trials natural capital premium with UK dairy farmers**', [modelling-better-business-case-study-feb-2018.pdf \(cam.ac.uk\)](https://www.cam.ac.uk) [Online: accessed 03/10/2022]

Welsh Government, Defra, Scottish Forestry, Forestry Commission (2020) '**Science and innovation strategy for forestry for Great Britain**'. Digital ISBN 978-1180082-329-7

Katy Joyce

Woodland Trust '**Croft Woodlands**', [Croft Woodlands - Woodland Trust - Woodland Trust](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Woodland Trust Scotland '**Scotland**' [Our Work in Scotland - Woodland Trust](#) [Online: accessed 28/09/2022]

World Bank Group, SRUC, Scottish Government, South of Scotland Enterprise, BioCarbon Fund (2022) '**Regional Land Use Partnership Pilots in Scotland**', [PowerPoint Presentation \(biocarbonfund-isfl.org\)](#) [Online: accessed 30/09/2022]

Appendix 1

Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches in the UK										
Lead Partner/s	Additional Partners / Contributors	Managed By	Date	Title	Location	Type of Intervention/s	Details	Link	Category of Government Decision	Reference
PRIVATE SECTOR INITIATED										
Nestle	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership's Natural Capital Impact Group, Anglian Water, Glanbia, Lactalis McLelland, Volac, Yara, Natural England, Environment Agency, Defra	Game & Wildlife Trust	2017-Current	Modelling Better Business	Cumbria & Ayrshire	Trial of: Dairy Action Research Laboratory approach Payment by Results (PbR)	Dairy farmers choose from a range of natural capital or carbon auditing intervention activities. They receive per-litre price premiums, paid twice yearly, for their stewardship of natural capital. Under the scheme, 'Working with Nature' programmes are run to provide training for improved natural capital management and animal welfare and antibiotics courses, for example.	modelling-better-business-case-study-feb-2018.pdf (cam.ac.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Capitals Coalition, 2022)
Wessex Water	Exeter University	Wessex Water	2017-Current	EnTrade	Somerset, Bristol Avon, & The Solent	Trading platform for reverse auctioning of nature-based solutions	Initial trades facilitated the fair payment of farmers for planting winter crops on their fields to reduce nitrate run-off in the Poole Harbour catchment. As of 2017 its trades covered 3,000ha of land and had resulted in the elimination of 40 tonnes of nitrogen, as well as saving Wessex Water 30% in compliance costs (Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017). They now use 'catchment markets', online marketplaces for the trade of nature-based projects, facilitating payments for landowners, risk avoidance and the achievement of environmental goals for investors. A fair market settlement process, designed with Exeter University, is used to match buyers and landholders and legal contracts are signed.	About us (entrade.co.uk)	Finance and Investment	(EnTrade, 2022)

Landscape Enterprise Network (LENS)		Landscape Enterprise Network (LENS)	2017 - Current	Landscape Enterprise Network (LENS)	Across the UK & Europe	Regional trading platform for nature-based solutions Blended finance	LENS delivers blended finance by revealing collaborative value chains for various landscape outcomes to identify common interests among public and private investors within a specific area and by brokering negotiations and transactions between buyers and groups of landowners who deliver services. Trades are currently occurring across the UK and in Europe. The first set of trades, valued at £1 million, were in the East of England between initial partners Nestle Purina, Cereal Partners UK, West Northamptonshire Council and Anglian Water who invested collaboratively in ecosystem service outcomes such as 'resilient agricultural supply chains, flood risk mitigation, water quality improvements, GHG emissions reduction, carbon sequestration and an increase in [regenerative] agricultural land management' (LENS, 2022). A second trade here is expected to be valued at around £2.5 million. Trades occurring in Cumbria with Nestle, United Utilities, First Milk, Eden Rivers Trust, the Environment Agency, Eden District Council and the National Trust are also delivering ecosystem service functions and bolstering farmer income while reducing business risk for investors and were initially valued at £700,000.	Landscape Enterprise Networks – A 3Keel initiative to support resilient landscapes.	Finance and Investment	(LENS, 2022)
Natural Infrastructure Schemes (NIS)	National Trust, Esmee Fairbairn Foundation, Interserve, Southern Water, United Utilities, Wessex Water, Green Alliance		2017	Natural Infrastructure Schemes (NIS)		Theoretical model for paying farmers for business risk avoidance	This model has so far been conceptualised for water attenuation projects whereby farmers 'engineer their land to deliver slow, clean water' (2017, p.2), but not yet trialled in practice.	Natural infrastructure schemes in practice.pdf (green-alliance.org.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017)

GOVERNMENT INITIATED										
Defra	Multiple Partners		2021	ELMS Trials	Multiple Locations	ELMS Blended finance Reverse Auctions	Blended finance options are being tested, for example in Cornwall AONB (Cornwall Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty, 2022) where a natural capital prospectus targeting various ecosystems including woodland services has been created with funding from the Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund to attract investment for collaborative nature and landscape recovery. Funds are matched by public Landscape Recovery funding and the AONB takes on the role of broker. A similar blended finance trial at Aqualate Mere highlighted a need for government support in deciding 'what can be traded' (p.22) and in providing 'support in setting a value-based system for the assets and accreditation' (p.22) for delivery. Reverse Auctions have been tested in 6 trials and found to be most successful for familiar interventions and at large scale.	Environmental land management: tests and trials - December 2021 (publishing.service.gov.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Defra, 2021, [7])
Forestry Commission			2021	Animation Activities	Greater Manchester, Merseyside, Cheshire, Greater London Authority	Prospectus of investment projects	Projects could be privately financed but do not necessarily focus around natural capital.	Environmental land management: tests and trials - December 2021 (publishing.service.gov.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Defra, 2021, [7])
Defra / HM Treasury	The Green Finance Institute, Environment Agency, Natural England, Access Foundation for Social Investment		2021	Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund	Multiple Locations	Grant funding	Set up to bolster natural capital projects to reach a stage of preparation necessary for attracting private investment. Currently the funding window is closed.	[Withdrawn] How to apply for a natural environment investment readiness fund grant - GOV.UK (www.gov.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Environment Agency, 2022)
Council for Sustainable Business			2022	Council for Sustainable Business		Advisory council of business leaders	Consisting of 15 business leaders, this was set up to provide advice to Defra on the involvement of businesses in environmental improvement as per the 25 Year Plan and has already	Home Page Council for Sustainable Business	Finance and Investment	(Council for Sustainable Business, 2022)

							engaged over 200 UK businesses with its aims.			
LOCAL AUTHORITY INITIATED										
The Rivers Trust	Defra, The Environment Agency		2022	Replenishing Nature, Establishing Commercial Governance & Future Trades for the Eden Catchment Market, Wyre Natural Flood Management Investment Readiness Project	Multiple Locations	Multi-buyer and -seller model Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund	The Rivers Trust is in the process of setting up a pilot using a multi-buyer and seller model wherein it would act as an intermediary for the brokering of private investment for nature-based solutions	Natural infrastructure schemes in practice.pdf (green-alliance.org.uk) New opportunities to invest in nature as The... The Rivers Trust	Finance and Investment	(Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017, and Rivers Trust, 2022)
Sheffield City Council	Sheffield Chamber of Commerce, the Environment Scheme		2014-2019	Lower Don Valley Defence Project	Sheffield	Business Improvement District Mechanism	An innovative collaboration between Sheffield City Council, the Sheffield Chamber of Commerce and the Environment Scheme (Sheffield City Council, 2022). Flood protection measures were improved by utilising a Business Improvement District Mechanism to obtain £1.4 million of investment from local businesses, 'collected as a levy on local rates' (Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017, p.17).	Natural infrastructure schemes in practice.pdf (green-alliance.org.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017)
Environment Agency	Eastbourne Borough Council / Rother District Council, Westminster Dredging Co Ltd., Dean and Dyball, Mackley Construction, Mouchel Group		2000	Pevensey Bay Flood Defences	Pevensey	Blended finance (Public Private Partnership)	the Pevensey Bay Flood Defences was the first sea defence project in the world to be funded by a consortium of four businesses and the Environment Agency in a 25-year contract (Pevensey Coastal Defence Ltd, 2022, Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017).	Natural infrastructure schemes in practice.pdf (green-alliance.org.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Andrews Tipper and Francis, 2017)
PAID SERVICE PROVISION										
Strutt & Parker	Economics for the Environment Consultancy (eftec)		2020		Multiple Locations	Paid Service Provision – Natural Capital Accounting	Collaboration between eftec and Strutt and Parker to provide natural capital accounting services to support ELMS requirements	Natural capital account collaboration with eftec Rural Hub Strutt & Parker (struttandparker.com)	Finance and Investment	(Strutt & Parker, 2020)

Appendix 2

Private Sector Involvement in Supporting Natural Capital Approaches in Scotland										
Lead Partner/s	Additional Partners / Contributors	Managed By	Date	Title	Location	Type of Intervention/s	Details	Link	Category of Government Decision	Reference
PRIVATE SECTOR INITIATED										
Baillie Gifford	Borders Forest Trust and others		2022		Multiple Locations	Philanthropic Support	Offer philanthropic support for charities and not-for-profits and have been instrumental in financing the natural capital work of the Borders Forest Trust, for example.	Our Story Global Long-term Active Asset & Investment Trust Manager Baillie Gifford Baillie Gifford	Finance and Investment	(Baillie Gifford, 2022)
GOVERNMENT INITIATED										
Scottish Government			2020	Green Investment Portfolio	Scotland	Prospectus of investment projects	This provides net zero investment opportunities worth £1 billion into 'low carbon, eco-friendly and recycling' projects.	Green Investment Portfolio launched - gov.scot (www.gov.scot)	Finance and Investment	(Scottish Government, 2020, [1])
Scottish Environment Protection Agency	Natural Environment Research Council, University of Edinburgh		2017-2018	Valuing Nature Programme	Spey Catchment	Research	The report explored the state of private investment into land management that protects natural capital, with a focus on the Spey catchment. It found that businesses understand how natural capital impacts business outcomes but find it hard to see where actual investment returns will come from. As a result, private investment into natural capital remains low. Businesses identified the need for intermediaries to coordinate investment and for government support in the development of a national investment framework using levies or a project-based model. They also identified the need for collaborative approaches amongst businesses who are often reluctant to invest in natural capital projects which may inadvertently benefit competitors.	'Understanding the potential for private sector investment in natural capital – lessons from the Spey catchment: Executive Summary', Executive summary (sepa.org.uk)	Finance and Investment	(Scottish Environment Protection Agency, and University of Edinburgh 2018)
SEPA, Scottish Wildlife Trust	Borders Forest Trust, Central Scotland Green Network Trust, Confor, Conservation Capital, City of Edinburgh Council, Ferry Hydro, Forest Carbon Ltd, Forestry and Land Scotland, Highlands and Islands Enterprise, IEMA, Jacobs UK Ltd, John	NCPF led by Conservation Capital NCB led by Abundance Investment & City of Edinburgh, LENS, Peatland Code / Woodland	2020	Route Map to £1 Billion including the Natural Capital Pioneer Fund, Nature-Climate Bond, LENS,	Scotland	Finance Routemap Investment Fund Climate Bond Carbon Payments Blended Finance And others	An innovative collective enterprise to map a route to securing £1 billion in investment for nature in Scotland to address biodiversity loss and facilitate action towards UN Sustainable Development Goals. The project brought together a large group of stakeholders to collaboratively consider how to go about this task. It proposed a number of initiatives, of particular interest are: 1) the Natural	202001_1-Billion-Challenge-Document_FINAL.pdf Riverwoods Scottish Wildlife Trust	Finance and Investment	(SEPA and Scottish Wildlife Trust, 2020)

	Muir Trust, Loch Lomond & The Trossachs National Park, Marine Conservation Society, National Trust for Scotland, Ridrum Group, Royal Zoological Society of Scotland, RSPB Scotland, Scottish Borders Council, Scottish Natural Heritage, Scottish Water, Scottish Wildlife Trust, SEPA, Shetland Amenity Trust, Southern Uplands Partnership, Sustainable Scotland Network, The Heather Trust, Tweed Forum, Woodland Trust Scotland, Zero Waste Scotland	Carbon Code, Riverwoods led by Scottish Wildlife Trust, Scottish Natural Heritage, SEPA, Tweed Forum, Confor, James Hutton Institute, University of Edinburgh, Woodland Trust Scotland, Scottish Forestry, Scottish Water		Nature Based Carbon Payments, Riverwoods and others			Capital Pioneer Fund, to be managed by conservation finance specialists, to match investors with businesses in need of unsecured loans for activities related to biodiversity enhancement and protection, with loans to be repaid at a later stage with business profits. 2) The Nature Climate Bond which would use crowdfunding to raise investment for bonds which would fund nature-based solutions. 3) Incorporation of activities with the LENS project (see above) 4) Nature-based Carbon Payments: 'Carbon Plus' which enables the purchasing of carbon credits via the Peatland Code and Woodland Carbon Code (see below) and 5) Riverwoods, a trial / model of a blended finance scheme for funding landscape-scale projects for biodiversity; Riverwood aims to create a network of riparian woodlands and biodiverse rivers, streams and lochs across Scotland. The Route Map notes the need for increased policy coherence, advice and support including skills building and seed funding, and continued cross-sectoral co-ordination including the development of common metrics for success.			
Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers (Scottish Forum on Natural Capital)	Scottish Wildlife Trust, SEPA, NatureScot, Scottish Forestry, Scotland's Rural College (SRUC), funded by the Esmee Fairbairn Foundation. Features strategic partnership arrangements with the Green Finance Initiative and Ecosystems Knowledge Network	Biodiversity Credits Programme led by Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers, Scottish Government, Scottish Wildlife Trust, NatureScot, CivTech	Since 2020	Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers / Innovate for Nature Challenge 8.6	Scotland	Stakeholder Network Biodiversity Credits	Provides a forum for a multi-actor network for exploring ways to generate new markets for investment in nature-based solutions in Scotland and bolster 'investment / investor readiness'. Propositions so far include the innovation of biodiversity credits and related markets as part of a CivTech Innovate for Nature challenge which aims to finance biodiversity enhancement and landscape recovery. Biodiversity credits are not intended to be used as an offset mechanism. Currently seeking applications from interested partners.	Scottish Forum on Natural Capital (naturalcapitalscotland.com) Scottish Nature Finance Pioneers – Grow, Restore, Prosper NatureScot Innovate for Nature – CivTech	Finance and Investment	(Scottish Forum on Natural Capital, 2022, NatureScot, 2022 [2], CivTech, 2022)
Scottish Forestry	Forestry Commission, Welsh Government, Northern Ireland Forest Service		Since 2011	UK Woodland Carbon Code	UK (but based in Scotland)	Carbon credits / market	An opportunity for investors to fund woodland creation via a quality assurance scheme which guarantees verifiable, ethical	Home - UK Woodland Carbon Code	Finance and Investment	(UK Woodland Carbon Code, 2022)

							carbon savings in return for carbon credits for offset against emissions.			
Scottish Wildlife Trust	Defra, Moors for the Future Partnership, National Trust for Scotland, Natural England, Natural Resources Wales, North Pennines Area of Natural Beauty (AONB) Partnership, Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB), Scottish Natural Heritage, Scottish Wildlife Trust, University of East London, University of Newcastle, Yorkshire Wildlife Trust, funded by the Esmee Fairbairn Foundation		Since 2015	International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) UK Peatland Code	UK (but based in Scotland)	Carbon credits / market	Aims to restore the UK's peatland. One mechanism for funding this is the availability of verifiable carbon credits for purchase by investors as part of a quality assurance scheme that can be offset against emissions.	IUCN UK Peatland Programme (iucn-uk-peatlandprogramme.org)	Finance and Investment	(IUCN, 2022)
PAID SERVICE PROVISION										
Scottish Woodlands			2022		Scotland	Group Certification Valuation Forest Mapping	Originally a woodland owner's cooperative, Scottish Woodlands is a primarily employee owned, forestry management, investment and acquisition service offering additional options to aid landowners in forest management and access to a group Certification scheme for UKWAS, FSC and PEFC. Various valuation and forestry mapping services are offered if landowners can afford to pay for them.	Investment Scottish Woodlands	Finance and Investment	(Scottish Woodlands, 2022) [2]

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